

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP

PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE 6.4 III part

MAPPING LOCAL INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1			
0.5			
0.9			
1			

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

ANALYSIS OF THE ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS OF IMPLEMENTING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS IN GRIP PROCESSES

AIM OF THE REPORT

The ultimate goal of RM6 consists of integrating the technological innovations developed by the other modules into operational platforms that can be concretely adopted by companies and public authorities through the model of Industrial Symbiosis (IS). This multidisciplinary approach encompasses regulatory, economic, environmental and social aspects. To ascertain the applicability of IS in the NODES territory, an operational model has been developed which is structured into several phases. These include mapping potentially involved companies, analysing relevant regulations, evaluating social acceptability, proposing rewarding criteria for public procurement (CAM) and assessing environmental and economic feasibility and preferability.

The present Deliverable 6.6 presents the work conducted by Task 6.6. During the course of the project, the scope of Task 6.6 underwent expansion. While the initial plan was to conduct a LCA analysis of specific GRIP processes, economic analyses were subsequently incorporated to evaluate economic convenience. This decision was made to ensure a comprehensive approach able to ascertain the feasibility of IS in its main dimensions. Consequently, the designation of Deliverable 6.6 was modified to emphasise the augmented scope of the task. The present report thus illustrates three different analyses conducted to assess the feasibility of IS in GRIP processes.

1. A **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** was conducted to evaluate the environmental preferability of the two GRIP processes,
2. A **Mathematical Optimisation Model** has been developed for the purpose of assessing the economic feasibility of IS. The model's primary focus is at the company level, and its

efficacy was assessed through a real-case study funded by the NODES project.

3. A **Cost-Benefit Analysis** (CBA) has been conducted, assessing the implementation of several RM1 processes in order to evaluate their economic benefits at the regional level.

Sommario

NODES Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile	1
ANALYSIS OF THE ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS OF IMPLEMENTING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS IN GRIP PROCESSES.....	3
AIM OF THE REPORT	3
PART I – LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF THE INVESTIGATED PROCESSES	11
1.1 OVERVIEW OF THE ANALYSES	11
1.2 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF TECHNOSOIL.....	12
<i>1.2.1 Goal and scope.....</i>	<i>12</i>
<i>1.2.2 Life Cycle Inventory: Life Cycle Inventory of fine recycled aggregates (screenunders) from Construction and demolition (C&D) waste.....</i>	<i>13</i>
<i>1.2.3 Life Cycle Inventory of quarried land and rocks (L&R).....</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>1.2.4 Life Cycle Inventory of compost.....</i>	<i>17</i>
<i>1.2.5 Life Cycle Impact Assessment.....</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>1.2.6 Interpretation and conclusions.....</i>	<i>22</i>
1.3 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF BEER FROM UNSOLD BREAD	23
<i>1.3.1 Goal and scope.....</i>	<i>23</i>
<i>1.3.2 Life Cycle Inventory: Life Cycle Inventory of Biova and Traditional beers.....</i>	<i>24</i>
<i>1.3.3 Life Cycle Impact Assessment and Interpretation.....</i>	<i>29</i>
1.4 CONCLUSIONS.....	34
PART II – MATHEMATICAL OPTIMISATION MODEL TO EVALUATE IS BENEFITS FOR A UTILISER COMPANY	36
2.1 OVERVIEW	36
2.2 METHODOLOGY.....	37
<i>2.2.1 The Framework.....</i>	<i>37</i>

2.2.2 Objective function	38
2.2.3 Model constraints	39
2.2.4 Model assumptions	39
2.2.5 Model utility	40
2.3 APPLICATION OF THE MODEL: CASE STUDY VEGEA	40
2.3.1 Company overview – Vegea	41
2.3.2 Application of the model to the base scenario	42
2.4 CONCLUSIONS	43
PART III – COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF IMPLEMENTING IS IN THE NODES AREA.....	44
3.1 OVERVIEW	44
3.2 REFERENCE FRAMEWORK	44
3.3 MODEL FORMULATION	45
3.3.1 Scenario BAU	47
3.3.2 Scenario of Symbiotic relationship	47
3.3.3 Discount rate and time horizon	48
3.3.4 Allocation of additional symbiosis costs	50
3.3.5 Emissions calculation	51
3.4 MODEL ASSUMPTIONS.....	52
3.5 APPLICATION OF THE CBA MODEL AT THE NODES SCALE.....	53
3.5.1 Definition of symbiotic flows and identification of potentially involved companies	53
3.5.2 Territorial mapping	54
3.5.3 Technical and economic data collection	58
3.5.4 Estimate of production scale using Monte Carlo simulation	62
3.5.5 Future scenarios and temporal dynamics	63
3.5.6 Calculation of avoided emissions	64
3.6 ANALYSIS OF SYMBIOTIC MATRICES	73
3.6.1 Fine mineral waste for the technosoil	73
3.6.2 Bottom ash for the cement and ceramics industries	73
3.6.3 Fly ash for the creation of geopolymers for ceramic products	74
3.6.4 Fly ash for metal recovery	74
3.6.5 Fired ceramic waste for the ceramic and cement industries	75
3.6.6 Industrial mineral waste for technical soil and/or base material for footing tracks	75
3.6.7 Coarse mineral waste for certifiable aggregates	76

3.6.8 Silicate rock quarry waste for rare earth enrichment	76
3.7 ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESULTS ANALYSIS	76
3.7.1 Economic analysis	77
3.7.1.1 Base NPV and cost allocation.....	77
3.7.1.2 Sensitivity analysis.....	78
3.7.1.3 Impact of company size.....	78
3.7.1.4 Inflation and technological innovation.....	79
3.7.2 Environmental analysis	79
3.8 SUMMARY OF RESULTS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS	80
3.8.1 Summary of results	80
3.8.2 Model limits	81
3.8.3 Future perspectives	81

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

NODES
Nord-Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

Summary of Tables

Table 1. Inventory for the phase of C&D waste collection.....	14
Table 2. Inventory for the phase of C&D waste digging, crushing and screening.....	14
Table 3. Inventory for the phase of quarried L&R collection	16
Table 4. Inventory for the phase of quarried L&R recovery.....	16
Table 5. Inventory for the phase of compost production.....	18
Table 6. Potential impacts of 1 t of technosoil	19
Table 7. Inventory for the phase of bread collection and grinding	24
Table 8. Inventory for the phase of mashing	25
Table 9. Inventory for the phase of boiling	26
Table 10. Inventory for the phase of brewing.....	26
Table 11. Inventory for the phase of centrifuging	27
Table 12. Inventory for the phase of packaging.....	28
Table 13. Inventory for the phase of glass recycling	28
Table 14. Potential impacts of 1 l of Biova beer and traditional beer.	31
Table 15. Computation of BAU costs.....	47
Table 16. The three possible outcomes of the symbiotic scenario.	47
Table 17. Ateco codes considered in RM1.....	54
Table 18. Main statistics obtained by the mapping.....	57
Table 19. Sources related to waste production rates.....	59
Table 20. Sources related to input consumption rates (or recovery rates)	59
Table 21. Sources related to the costs of treating product matrices	60
Table 22. Sources related to special waste disposal costs	61
Table 23. Sources related to the purchase costs of virgin raw materials	61
Table 24. Companies classification according to their size.....	62
Table 25. CO2 emissions for each matrix.....	66

Summary of Figures

Figure 1. System boundaries of the study	13
Figure 2. Impact on climate change of 1 t of technosoil (visualization cutoff: 1%)	20
Figure 3. Sensitivity analysis: potential impact of 1 t of technosoil using different energy sources.....	21
Figure 4. Flow chart of the LCA study developed for the Biova and traditional beers.....	24
Figure 5. Flow chart of a bottle of beer, considering also the end-of-life of the packaiging (visualization cut-off: 1%).....	30
Figure 6. Comparison of potential impacts of Biova beer and Traditional beer (relative values).....	32
Figure 7. Chart of climate change potential impact of 1 l of Biova beer.....	33
Figure 8. Chart of climate change potential impact of 1 l of traditional beer.	34
Figure 9. Current Vegea's sourcing setup.....	42
Figure 10. Optimised Allocation of residues across the suppliers.....	42
Figure 11. Production process of companies α and β	46
• Figure 12. Mapping companies within the NODES territory.....	56
Figure 13. Mapping Special waste Landfills within the NODES territory	56
Figure 14. Roads accessible by companies to landfills.	57

Part I – LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF THE INVESTIGATED PROCESSES

1.1 Overview of the analyses

Task 6.6 focuses on IS and the development of a general framework for LCA in circular economy applications. The transition toward a circular economy requires an approach to resource management that goes beyond traditional linear production and consumption models. IS is a possible strategy in this context, enabling different industrial actors to exchange materials, energy, and by-products in ways that reduce waste, improve resource efficiency, and create new value chains. By integrating waste streams from multiple sectors into productive processes, industrial symbiosis not only minimizes environmental burdens but also fosters economic and social benefits within regional industrial ecosystems. LCA provides a robust methodological framework to evaluate the environmental performance of such circular economy interventions. By assessing impacts across the full life cycle of a product or process—from raw material extraction to end-of-life—LCA identifies environmental hotspots, informs design and operational decisions, and supports the development of sustainable production strategies. When applied to circular economy and industrial symbiosis initiatives, LCA allows stakeholders to verify whether the valorisation of waste streams delivers tangible environmental benefits, while also quantifying trade-offs across different impact categories.

Within this framework, the study presents **two illustrative case studies**. The first, **Technosoil**, involves large-scale valorisation of inert and organic waste to produce a functional soil substitute for construction applications. This project exemplifies IS at an industrial scale, where waste streams from multiple sectors are integrated to create a product with both functional and environmental value. The second case study, Biova **beer**, demonstrates circular economy principles at the consumer-product level, partially substituting malt with unsold bread to reduce the environmental footprint of beer production. This case highlights how food waste can be valorised while promoting consumer awareness of sustainable practices. By combining these two case studies, this task provides insights into both large-scale industrial and small-scale consumer-level circular interventions. LCA is employed to systematically quantify environmental impacts, identify key drivers, and evaluate enabling conditions such as energy sources, transport logistics, substitution rates, and packaging end-of-life management. Furthermore, LCA could be integrated with complementary tools, such as circularity indicators, to provide a broader and more holistic assessment of resource efficiency and sustainability performance.

The aim of this activity is twofold: to demonstrate how LCA can quantify the environmental benefits and limitations of circular economy interventions, and to provide evidence-based guidance for designing strategies that maximize the sustainability potential of IS and waste

valorisation initiatives. Through this work, the study contributes to the methodological framework of the NODES project while advancing practical knowledge on the implementation of circular economy principles in both industrial and consumer contexts.

1.2 Life Cycle Assessment of technosoil

The LCA developed as first case study investigates the production of technosoil. This is a technical solution already implemented at full scale, developed by Cave Fassino (Pianezza, Turin). The technosoil is composed by fine aggregates recycled from construction and demolition (C&D) waste, quarried land and rocks (L&R) waste and compost obtained from green waste and Water Treatment Plant (WTP) dried sludge.

1.2.1 Goal and scope

In a LCA study, it is essential to clearly define the objectives in order to ensure that the tool can capture all environmental implications associated with the analysed system and provide consistent answers to the relevant research questions.

This study, conducted within the framework of the NODES project, has the main objective of analysing and quantifying the environmental impacts generated by the production of **1 ton of technosoil** (defined as **functional unit** of the LCA study) obtained from waste materials. The specific goal is to evaluate whether technosoil production can represent a solution that combines good environmental performance with the management of inert and biogenic waste, while also promoting industrial symbiosis.

The definition of **system boundaries** represents one of the most crucial and delicate aspects of an LCA study, since the choices made in this phase significantly impact the final results and their interpretation. It is therefore essential to establish precisely which phases of the product life cycle and which segments of the production chain are included in the analysis. This step allows to ensure methodological coherence and completeness in the assessment of environmental impacts. The flow chart in Figure 1 shows the system boundaries, i.e. the processes/steps included in the assessment. Each process of the value chain is detailed in the Life Cycle Inventory paragraph.

All data employed in the model for the production of fine aggregates, quarried L&R, compost and for the production of the technosoil are primary data. These data were collected through questionnaires filled out by company representatives in 2025 and referred to the solar year 2024. The IT tools supporting the development and analysis of the LCA model are the following:

- LCA Software: SimaPro 9.6.0.1
- LCA database: The Ecoinvent 3.10 database developed by the Swiss Centre for Life Cycle Assessment was used as a source of selected generic data.

Figure 1. System boundaries of the study

1.2.2 Life Cycle Inventory: Life Cycle Inventory of fine recycled aggregates (screenunders) from Construction and demolition (C&D) waste

Construction and demolition (C&D) waste is collected from various construction sites located in the surroundings of Cave Fassino (Pianezza, TO). In 2024, a total of 21 tons of C&D waste was collected from 29 construction sites situated at distances ranging from 3 to 84 km from Cave Fassino, with a weighted average transport distance of 25 km. The waste was transported using lorries with payload capacities varying between 4.5 and 30 tons, with a weighted average payload of 24 tons. Table 1 summarized the inventory data used to model the C&D waste collection. At the Cave Fassino plant, C&D waste undergoes a series of processing steps including excavation, crushing, and screening. Primary data were used to quantify the duration of equipment usage and the resulting diesel consumption for these operations. The process yields three co-products: large recycled aggregates (30–70 mm), medium recycled aggregates (15–30 mm), and fine recycled aggregates (screenunders). A mass-based allocation approach was applied to distribute the environmental impacts among these three co-products. The inventory is detailed in Table 2.

Table 1. Inventory for the phase of C&D waste collection

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
C&D waste collected, at Cave Fassino	1	t		
INPUTS				
C&D waste	1	t		
Transport with lorry	25	tkm	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, S	Average transport distance: 25 km. Average payload: 24 t

Table 2. Inventory for the phase of C&D waste digging, crushing and screening

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Large recycled aggregates (30-70 mm)	0.2	t		Allocation by mass: 20%
Medium recycled aggregates (15-30 mm)	0.3	t		Allocation by mass: 30%
Fine recycled aggregated	0.5	t		Allocation by mass: 50%
INPUT				
C&D waste collected,	1	t		

at Cave Fassino				
Digging	2.55	kWh	Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for diesel, burned in building machine Cut-off, S	Data for 21 t: 0.25 h of use of excavator, diesel consumption: 20 l/h. Energy density of diesel: 10.7 kWh/l
Digger	3.75*10 ⁻⁷	p	Hydraulic digger {RER} hydraulic digger production Cut-off, S	20000 hours of lifetime
Crushing	1.16	kWh	Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for diesel, burned in building machine Cut-off, S	Data: 0.108 l/t. Energy density of diesel: 10.7 kWh/l
Crusher	9.4*10 ⁻⁶	t	Industrial machine, heavy, unspecified {RER} market for industrial machine, heavy, unspecified Cut-off, S	20000 hours of lifetime. Assumed 25 t per crusher
Screening	0.71	kWh	Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for diesel, burned in building machine Cut-off, S	Data: 0.067 l/t. Energy density of diesel: 10.7 kWh/l
Sieve	1.9*10 ⁻⁶	t	Industrial machine, heavy, unspecified {RER} market for industrial machine, heavy, unspecified Cut-off, S	20000 hours of lifetime. Assumed 5 t per sieve

1.2.3 Life Cycle Inventory of quarried land and rocks (L&R)

Residues from the quarrying activities connected to different construction sites are recovered and used as material for the technosoil.

In 2024, a total of 22 tons of quarried L&Rs was collected from 19 construction sites situated at distances ranging from 3 to 84 km from Cave Fassino, with a weighted average transport distance of 15 km. The waste was transported using lorries with payload capacities varying between 4 and 30 tons, with a weighted average payload of 23 tons. At Cave Fassino an excavator is used for

moving the quarried L&R. Tables 3 and 4 summarise the inventory data used to model the C&D waste collection and recovery.

Table 3. Inventory for the phase of quarried L&R collection

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Quarried L&R collected, at Cave Fassino	1	t		
INPUTS				
Stone	1	t		Elementary flow
Transport with lorry	15	tkm	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, S	Average transport distance: 15 km. Average payload: 23 t

Table 4. Inventory for the phase of quarried L&R recovery

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Quarried L&R, recovered	1	t		
INPUT				
Quarried L&R collected, at Cave Fassino	1	t		Elementary flow
Digging	7.13	kWh	Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for diesel, burned in building machine Cut-off, S	Data for 3 t: 0.1 h of use of excavator, diesel consumption: 20 l/h.

				Energy density of diesel: 10.7 kWh/l
Digger	1,67*10-6	p	Hydraulic digger {RER} hydraulic digger production Cut-off, S	20000 hours of lifetime

1.2.4 Life Cycle Inventory of compost

Compost is produced by CIDIU in Rivoli (Turin). CIDIU carries out composting using two main input materials:

- Sewage sludge, sourced from SMAT and AIDA treatment plants;
- Green waste, such as grass clippings and prunings, collected from 17 municipalities and private gardeners.

A third component, sovallo (the coarse fraction of compost that doesn't pass screening), is reintroduced into the process. Though it degrades slowly, it helps provide structure to the compost. Its proportion varies seasonally.

The composting process includes six main phases:

1. Shredding of green waste using diesel-powered machinery.
2. Mixing of shredded green waste, sludge, and sovallo in an electric mixer.
3. Sanitization in sealed bio-cells with heated air (above 55°C for at least 3 days), followed by air treatment using scrubbers and bio-filters.
4. Primary maturation for 60 days in ventilated piles, turned regularly with diesel-powered loaders.
5. Screening to separate fine compost from coarse sovallo, which is reused.
6. Final maturation for 30 days, followed by chemical analysis.

At the end of the 90-day process, the compost is sold. About 10% of the produced compost is used for technosoil. The site uses 100% renewable electricity and manages emissions (methane, ammonia, VOCs, and vapor) with two bio-filters and a scrubber. Percolate and wastewater are sent to SMAT for treatment. For confidentiality reasons, the inventory provided by the company is aggregated in a unique process, as indicated in Table 5.

Table 5. Inventory for the phase of compost production.

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Compost	1	t		
Leachate	0.63	m ³	Leachate, SLF, wood ash mixture, pure {Europe without Switzerland} market for leachate, SLF, wood ash mixture, pure Cut-off, S	
INPUT				
Green waste	1.53	t	-	
Green waste transport	1.53*13.7 = 21	tkm	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, S	13.7 average weighted distance
WTP dried sludge	1.42	t	-	
WTP dried sludge transport	1.42*19.2 = 27.3	tkm	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, S	19.2 average weighted distance
Electricity	288	kWh	Electricity, low voltage {IT} electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted Cut-off, S	100% renewable energy
Diesel for green shredder and green sieve	2.58	l	Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for diesel, burned in building machine Cut-off, S	0.028 l/MJ
Diesel for wheel loaders and trucks	5.46	l	Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for diesel, burned in building machine Cut-off, S	0.028 l/MJ

1.2.5 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Potential impacts for 1 t of technosoil have been calculated using EF 3.1 method and results are listed in Table 6:

Table 6. Potential impacts of 1 t of technosoil

Impact category	Unit of measure	Total
Acidification	mol H+ eq	1.27E-01
Climate change	kg CO2 eq	1.85E+01
Ecotoxicity, freshwater - part 1	CTUe	1.06E+02
Ecotoxicity, freshwater - part 2	CTUe	4.25E+01
Ecotoxicity, freshwater - inorganics	CTUe	1.21E+02
Ecotoxicity, freshwater - organics - p.1	CTUe	2.60E+01
Ecotoxicity, freshwater - organics - p.2	CTUe	1.80E+00
Particulate matter	disease inc.	2.91E-06
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	4.63E-02
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	3.84E-03
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	5.03E-01
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	1.15E-07
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	3.95E-07
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq	5.22E-01
Land use	Pt	7.37E+01
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.35E-07
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	1.62E-01
Resource use, fossils	MJ	2.44E+02
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	3.21E-04
Water use	m3 depriv.	-6.35E-01

Figure 2 shows the chart related to the potential impact on climate change, where the thickness of each arrow is directly proportional to the contribution. As can be observed, the largest share of the impact is associated with the energy required for compost production (diesel and electricity). It is important to highlight that the electricity used in the CIDIU plant is 100% renewable, assumed generated entirely from photovoltaic panels. To evaluate how the source of electricity influences the final impact of technosoil production, a sensitivity analysis was performed by recalculating the impacts with four different energy supply options: (i) Italian energy mix, (ii) Italian residual energy mix, (iii) hydroelectric energy, and (iv) photovoltaic energy.

As shown in Figure 3, the energy mix strongly affects all the analysed indicators. With regard to climate change, the final results vary significantly depending on the electricity source: 14.5 kg CO₂ eq/t with hydroelectric energy, 18.5 kg CO₂ eq/t with photovoltaic energy, 35.7 kg CO₂ eq/t with the Italian energy mix, and 51.1 kg CO₂ eq/t with the residual energy mix.

Figure 2. Impact on climate change of 1 t of technosoil (visualization cutoff: 1%)

Figure 3. Sensitivity analysis: potential impact of 1t of technosoil using different energy sources.

1.2.6 Interpretation and conclusions

The case of technosoil highlights the potential of IS. By combining inorganic waste (construction and demolition waste + quarried land and rocks) with organic waste (compost), a new secondary product is generated that provides both environmental and practical benefits. This integration reduces the pressure on landfills, substitutes primary raw materials, and promotes circularity in two waste streams that are usually managed separately. The sensitivity analysis also shows that when coupled with low-impact energy sources, such symbiotic processes can deliver competitive environmental performances on climate change, turning waste management challenges into opportunities for resource efficiency and climate mitigation.

In conclusion, technosoil production demonstrates how IS, supported by renewable energy, can create innovative pathways to valorise waste while lowering environmental impacts. This approach represents a promising strategy to reconcile waste management with resource efficiency and climate goals.

1.3 Life Cycle Assessment of beer from unsold bread

This paragraph introduces a second case study of industrial symbiosis: the production of beer that partially substitutes malt with unsold bread. Specifically, Biova Project was established as an innovative start-up with the aim of reducing food waste by valorising surplus products from the agri-food supply chain. The company's flagship product, Biova Classica beer, is brewed using unsold bread as a partial substitute for barley malt. This approach not only prevents the disposal of an organic waste still rich in nutritional value but also contributes to lowering the environmental impacts associated with cereal cultivation and processing. The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology represents an appropriate tool to objectively and consistently evaluate the environmental impacts associated with the entire production process of Biova beer. It highlights the potential benefits generated by a circular economy approach, while also identifying possible criticalities along the supply chain.

The present LCA focuses on a production batch of Biova Classica (Kölsch style) beer, characterized by an alcohol content of 4.67% Vol, a final density of 11.2 °Plato, and a colour value of 7.9 EBC.

1.3.1 Goal and scope

This study, conducted within the framework of the NODES project, has the main objective of analysing and quantifying the environmental impacts generated by the production of 1 l of beer (defined as functional unit of the LCA study) obtained from using unsold bread and to compare it with traditional beer. The specific goal is to evaluate whether and in which measure this technology can reduce the environmental impacts of beer.

The system boundaries are from-cradle-to-grave and consider the production of the beer starting from the raw materials, the packaging into brown glass bottles of 33 cl and a recycling scenario for the glass. The distribution of bottles to the consumer is not considered because of the high uncertainty and variability of distances and means of transport. As shown in the flow chart of Figure 4, the production process of Biova beer is largely the same as that of traditional beer. The main difference lies in the partial substitution of malt with bread. Consequently, the Biova process also includes the collection of unsold bread and its grinding, as detailed in the inventory phase. Since the packaging is identical for both beer types and the End-of-Life scenario of the glass bottle depends mainly on consumer behaviour, further details are focused on the production stage of the beer prior to packaging.

Most data employed in the model for the production of beer are primary data provided by Biova Project srl. These data were collected through questionnaires filled out by company representatives in 2025. Missing information have been integrated with literature studies. The IT tools supporting the development and analysis of the LCA model are the following:

- LCA Software: SimaPro 9.6.0.1
- LCA database: The Ecoinvent 3.10 database developed by the Swiss Centre for Life

Cycle Assessment was used as a source of selected generic data.

Figure 4. Flow chart of the LCA study developed for the Biova and traditional beers.

1.3.2 Life Cycle Inventory: Life Cycle Inventory of Biova and Traditional beers

The following tables present the detailed inventory data for both Biova beer and traditional beer. In particular, Table 7 refers exclusively to Biova beer, as they include the collection and grinding of unsold bread. Table 8, which relates to the mashing process, provides partially separate inventory data for the two beer types, while Tables 9-13 apply to both beers.

For the end-of-life phase, a scenario is considered in which the brown glass bottle is recycled to produce new brown glass. The avoided product is assumed to be the same type of glass manufactured entirely from primary raw materials. The end-of-life of the label is excluded from the analysis due to its negligible mass and the high uncertainty associated with its disposal pathway.

Table 7. Inventory for the phase of bread collection and grinding

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Ground bread	150	kg		
INPUT				
Unsold bread	150	kg		
Transport with van	1125	kgkm	Transport, freight, light commercial vehicle {Europe without Switzerland} market	

			for transport, freight, light commercial vehicle Cut-off, S	
Electricity	1	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} electricity, medium voltage, residual mix Cut-off, S	

Table 8. Inventory for the phase of mashing

Flow	Quantity for Biova beer	Quantity for Traditional beer	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset
OUTPUT				
Mashed must	3183		l	
INPUT				
Ground bread	150	0	kg	
Water	3600		l	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for tap water Cut-off, S
Malt	422	500	kg	Modeled from: Moresi and Cimini, 2025, Effect of Malthouse Size and Transportation on the Environmental Profile of Malt Production
Electricity	6		kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} electricity, medium voltage, residual mix Cut-off, S
Steam	30		kg	Steam, in chemical industry {RER} market for steam, in chemical industry Cut-off, S
Heat	3024		MJ	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} market for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, S
	Literature value from: Cordella et al., (2008), LCA of an Italian lager beer. The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment			

Table 9. Inventory for the phase of boiling

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Boiled must	2950	l		Allocation: 100%
Brewer spent grains	914	l		Allocation: 0% (because it has no market value)
Waste: protein residues at the bottom	30	l	Proxy: Wastewater from potato starch production {CH} market for wastewater from potato starch production Cut-off, S	
INPUT				
Mashed must	3183	l		
Hop	6.378	kg	EF database: Hop pellets_at plant_EU-28+3_S	
Heat	33.08	MJ	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {Europe without Switzerland} market for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, S	

Table 10. Inventory for the phase of brewing

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Brewed beer	2750	l		
Waste: purge from tank bottoms	100	l	Wastewater from potato starch production {CH} market for wastewater from potato starch production Cut-off, S	
INPUT				
Boiled must	2950	l		

Yeast	3.835	kg	Fodder yeast {CH} ethanol production from whey Cut-off, S	
Nitrogen	94	kg	Nitrogen, liquid {RER} market for nitrogen, liquid Cut-off, S	
Electricity	66.16	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} electricity, medium voltage, residual mix Cut-off, S	

Table 11. Inventory for the phase of centrifuging

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Centrifugated beer	2650	l		
Waste: purge from tank bottoms	100	l	Wastewater from potato starch production {CH} market for wastewater from potato starch production Cut-off, S	
INPUT				
Brewed beer	2750	l		
Electricity	10	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} electricity, medium voltage, residual mix Cut-off, S	Average value

Table 12. Inventory for the phase of packaging

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Bottle of beer	2640	l		Corresponding to 8000 bottles of 0.33 l
INPUT				
Centrifugated beer	2640	l		
Electricity	87	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} electricity, medium voltage, residual mix Cut-off, S	Average value
Glass bottle	1920	kg	Packaging glass, brown {RER w/o CH+DE} packaging glass production, brown Cut-off, S	Brown bottles of 0.33 l. Weight per bottle: 0.24 kg
Label	3.2	kg	Printed paper {Europe without Switzerland} operation, printer, laser, colour, per kg printed paper Cut-off, S	
Carbon dioxide	30	kg	Carbon dioxide, liquid {RER} carbon dioxide production, liquid Cut-off, S	

Table 13. Inventory for the phase of glass recycling

Flow	Quantity	Unit of measure	Ecoinvent dataset	Notes
OUTPUT				
Recycled glass (avoided product)	1	l	Packaging glass, brown {GLO} packaging glass production,	Assumption: the avoided product is brown glass from

			brown, without cullet Cut-off, S	virgin raw materials
INPUT				
Waste glass	0.75	kg		Assumption: the recycled glass is composed by 75% of glass cullet and 25% of virgin raw materials.
Recycling of glass	1	kg	Packaging glass, brown {DE} packaging glass production, brown Cut-off, S	

1.3.3 Life Cycle Impact Assessment and Interpretation

Potential impacts were calculated for both Biova beer and traditional beer. The first assessment considered the entire life cycle of a bottle of beer, from cradle to grave, including the recycling scenario for the glass bottle. As illustrated in Figure 5, which shows the potential climate change impact of Biova beer, the end-of-life scenario of the glass packaging plays a dominant role in the overall impact. Specifically, when a cradle-to-gate perspective is applied (i.e., excluding end-of-life), the packaging accounts for 72% of the total impact of a bottle of beer. However, this contribution is almost entirely offset when recycling assumptions, as described in the inventory phase, are applied. In other words, if the glass packaging is neither reused nor recycled, it represents the primary contributor to the impact of the product. Conversely, under responsible glass waste management, and given that both beer types share identical packaging, the focus of the impact assessment is shifted to the beer production phase, excluding packaging. To this end, the impacts of 1 litre of Biova beer are compared with those of 1 litre of traditional beer. Impact values, calculated using the EF 3.1 method, are reported in Table 14. The graph in Figure 6 shows the relative values.

Figure 5. Flow chart of a bottle of beer, considering also the end-of-life of the packaging (visualization cut-off: 1%).

Table 14. Potential impacts of 1 l of Biova beer and traditional beer.

	Unit	Biova beer	Traditional beer
Acidification	mol H+ eq	8.91E-04	9.99E-04
Climate change	kg CO2 eq	2.33E-01	2.55E-01
Ecotoxicity, freshwater - inorganics	CTUe	6.01E-01	6.88E-01
Particulate matter	disease inc.	1.87E-08	2.17E-08
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	1.09E-03	1.27E-03
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	1.11E-04	1.29E-04
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	8.32E-03	9.68E-03
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	8.31E-10	8.61E-10
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	2.63E-08	2.83E-08
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq	1.07E-02	1.14E-02
Land use	Pt	3.85E+01	4.52E+01
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.13E-08	1.27E-08
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	7.32E-04	8.18E-04
Resource use, fossils	MJ	2.79E+00	2.98E+00
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	7.85E-07	9.06E-07
Water use	m3 depriv.	1.33E-01	1.37E-01

Figure 6. Comparison of potential impacts of Biova beer and Traditional beer (relative values)

As shown by the results, the climate change impact associated with 1 litre of beer is 0.233 kg CO₂ eq for Biova beer and 0.255 kg CO₂ for traditional beer. Biova beer results having lower potential impacts across all the analysed indicators. The relative benefit ranges from 3% to 15%, with an average improvement of approximately 10% across all indicators. Although this does not represent a substantial reduction, Biova beer nonetheless contributes to lowering the overall environmental impacts of beer production.

Figures 7 and 8 present the flow charts of the two beer types. As can be observed, malt plays a significant role in both systems, contributing 53% of the impact in Biova beer and 57% in traditional beer. This indicates that substituting malt with ingredients of lower environmental impact—such as unsold bread—is a promising strategy to reduce impacts. However, since the substitution involves only 15% of the malt used in traditional beer, the corresponding environmental benefit is necessarily limited.

Heat also represents a major contributor to the climate change indicator, accounting for 36–37% of the total impact, while electricity contributes 8–9%. Consequently, another effective strategy for reducing impacts would be to decrease overall energy demand or to source energy from more sustainable alternatives, such as renewables.

The relatively short distance required for collecting the bread used in Biova beer (7.5 km) contributes to its overall lower impact compared to traditional beer. However, if the collection

distance were to exceed 150 km, the environmental benefit of substituting bread for malt would be completely offset.

Figure 7. Chart of climate change potential impact of 1l of Biova beer.

Figure 8. Chart of climate change potential impact of 1 l of traditional beer.

1.4 Conclusions

The two case studies—Technosoil and Biova beer—offer insights into how LCA can be applied to evaluate innovative circular economy solutions that valorise waste streams and promote resource efficiency.

Technosoil represents a large-scale, industrial symbiosis initiative where inert and organic waste materials are combined to produce a functional substitute for natural soil in construction applications. The LCA results clearly show that the environmental performance of this product is largely determined by energy use, particularly electricity. The sensitivity analysis demonstrates that when renewable sources such as hydroelectric or photovoltaic power are employed, the overall environmental burden decreases substantially. This underlines how circular products, while conceptually promising, rely heavily on systemic conditions such as energy infrastructure to reach their full environmental potential. Beyond energy aspects, the Technosoil case illustrates

the value of industrial symbiosis: waste materials that would otherwise require disposal are reintegrated into production cycles, reducing both landfill pressures and the demand for primary raw materials. This makes Technosoil not only a technological innovation but also an example of how cross-sectoral collaboration can strengthen the resilience and sustainability of regional economies.

Biova beer, by contrast, demonstrates how circular economy concepts can be operationalized at the consumer-product level, with a strong communicative and awareness-raising dimension. By partially substituting malt with unsold bread, Biova reduces the environmental footprint of beer production, achieving improvements ranging from 3% to 15% across different impact categories. The results highlight the importance of logistics and substitution rate: while short collection distances (≈ 7.5 km) ensure a net benefit, longer distances (>150 km) would negate the environmental advantage, showing that transport is a critical parameter in scaling up such initiatives. In addition, the Biova case underlines the crucial role of packaging and of their end-of-life scenarios in assessing environmental performance. The glass bottle constitutes the major contributor to climate change impacts if end-of-life is not considered, accounting for over 70% of the total impact in a cradle-to-gate analysis. Responsible management of glass waste through recycling substantially reduces this contribution, demonstrating that packaging strategies and consumer behaviour are critical factors in the overall sustainability of consumer products. This highlights that, for circular economy interventions at the product level, attention to both ingredient substitution and packaging end-of-life management is essential.

Taken together, the two cases illustrate complementary dimensions of the circular economy. Technosoil emphasizes systemic change through industrial symbiosis and large-scale waste valorisation, while Biova beer highlights niche but visible interventions that combine environmental benefits with consumer engagement. Both demonstrate that the success of circular strategies depends on enabling conditions—efficient logistics, optimized substitution rates, sustainable energy sources, and integration into broader value chains.

Finally, these studies confirm the crucial role of LCA as a decision-support tool in evaluating circular initiatives. LCA provides a robust framework to quantify environmental trade-offs, identify hotspots, and support the design of more sustainable systems. However, to capture the multidimensional nature of circularity, LCA should be complemented with additional approaches, such as material flow analysis and circularity indicators, which can provide further insights into resource efficiency, material loops, and systemic resilience. Integrating LCA with these tools enables a broader and more holistic assessment, ensuring that circular economy solutions are not only innovative in concept, but also environmentally effective, resource-efficient, and socially meaningful in practice.

Part II – MATHEMATICAL OPTIMISATION MODEL TO EVALUATE IS BENEFITS FOR A UTILISER COMPANY

2.1 Overview

The mathematical optimisation model developed by Task 6.6 provides an ex-ante assessment of an IS set-up from the perspective of a company that could potentially use production residues. The model was, in fact, developed at the company level. Specifically, it applied to symbiotic Utiliser, testing the economic convenience of engaging in symbiotic transactions. As previously illustrated in Deliverable 6.4, IS transactions involve at least two actors:

- The **producer**, i.e. the company that generates a reusable residue (e.g. by-products, residues, etc.)
- The **utiliser**, i.e. the entity that uses these residues as inputs in its own production processes, as a substitute or alongside virgin raw materials.

This work focuses exclusively on the second actor in the symbiotic exchange, the utiliser, who is often identified as the more vulnerable party within the IS network. While the producer merely provides waste material, the utiliser must integrate it into their production cycle, facing various challenges in the process:

- Operational, such as adapting existing facilities or pre-treating materials;
- Strategic, such as evaluating the risks associated with irregular supply;
- Economic, including investment requirements, transformation costs, and transport expenses.

By contrast, the producer tends to represent a more stable figure in the symbiotic relationship, as their economic motivation – reducing disposal costs or converting a waste stream into a profitable resource – is both direct and easily quantifiable. Moreover, in most cases, the residue is an inevitable by-product or waste of the production process, and its availability is therefore relatively constant and predictable. As a result, the producer is structurally less exposed to the operational barriers that often hinder the implementation of symbiosis. On the other hand, the user bears most of the uncertainty, as they must decide whether to modify their sourcing strategy and reconfigure their production processes, either partially or entirely. For this reason, recent literature has emphasised the importance of adopting the perspective of individual actors within the symbiotic network rather than focusing solely on the system-level efficiency of the network as a whole (Harfeldt-Berg et al., 2022). However, existing analytical models largely remain centred on system optimisation and efficiency. Against this backdrop, the proposed model aims to

address this methodological shortcoming by offering a tool designed specifically to support the decision-making process of the user entity within an industrial symbiosis context.

2.2 Methodology

The analysis aims to determine the economic feasibility of an IS configuration from the standpoint of a single actor – the utiliser - who is considering the opportunity to substitute virgin raw materials with production residues. The primary objective is to verify whether the utiliser can obtain a net economic benefit from this substitution by considering the purchase cost of the residues, as well as additional expenses related to logistics and material treatment to make them suitable for use. This also includes the potential activation of in-house processing facilities. This type of ex-ante assessment is valuable for companies approaching IS for the first time, as well as for those already involved in such practices who wish to expand or diversify their supplier network. To address this requirement, a mathematical **optimisation methodology based on linear programming** has been adopted. This approach enables the integrated and simultaneous management of the key variables involved in complex decision-making, including:

- The type of residue to be used;
- The supplier from which to source the residue;
- The quantity to be acquired;
- The most efficient treatment option (internal or external).

The model is designed to minimise the total cost incurred by the utiliser, calculated as the sum of all the above-mentioned components. It also incorporates realistic operational constraints, such as internal demand and the availability of residues at supplier sites, as well as the maximum treatment capacities of processing plants. A further strength lies in the possibility of simulating various alternative procurement scenarios, including hybrids, with the ultimate aim of supporting the decision-making process through a comparative evaluation of different strategic options. Thus, with a view to allocative efficiency, it steers the company's choices towards an economically optimal configuration. The elaborated model can be easily updated and parameterised, including new suppliers, new types of waste or economic constraints, guaranteeing a certain flexibility but also scalability.

2.2.1 The Framework

The model is a Linear Programming Model (LPM), designed to simulate the rational behaviour of a utiliser aiming to minimise the total cost associated with IS. These costs include purchase, transportation, and transformation costs of alternative inputs (i.e. production residues) compared to virgin raw materials.

The model includes the following sets and indices:

- $i \in \{1, \dots, I\}$: set of firms supplying residues

- $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$: set of residue types

The decision variables are:

- x_{ik} : quantity of residue type k purchased by the user from supplier i
- $z_k \in \{0,1\}$: binary variable indicating whether the internal treatment plant of the user for residue type k is activated (1 if active, 0 otherwise)

The main parameters are defined as follows:

- **CT_{ik}** : unit transportation cost of residue k from supplier i to the user
- **CP_{ik}** : unit purchase price of residue k from supplier i (this cost may be zero if the supplier disposes of the residue free of charge)
- **$Ckin$** : unit cost of treating residue k at the user's internal treatment facility
- **$Ckout$** : unit cost of treating residue k at an external facility (assumed to be independent of the supplier)
- **Fk** : fixed cost of activating the user's internal treatment facility for residue type k
- **ak** : share of the purchased quantity of residue k that requires treatment ($ak \in [0,1]$, where $ak = 0$ no treatment required; $ak = 1$ all purchased residue of type k must be treated).
- **dk** : total demand for residue k by the user
- **q_{ik}** : maximum available quantity of residue k at supplier i
- **cap_k** : maximum treatment capacity of the user's internal facility for residue type k
- **M** : a sufficiently large constant used to bind capacity constraints; defined such that $M \geq \max_k(cap_k)$

2.2.2 Objective function

The objective function represents the total cost incurred by the utiliser, assuming that only the following cost components are considered: purchase, transportation, and (optional) transformation of the residues. The goal is to minimise these costs with respect to the two decision variables of the model:

1. the quantity to be purchased from each supplier in order to meet the overall demand, and
2. the possibility of activating an internal treatment facility, which involves fixed activation costs (varying by residue type).

The objective function is expressed as follows:

$$\min\{\sum_{i \in I} \sum_{k \in K} (C_{Pik} + C_{Tik}) \cdot x_{ik} + \sum_{k \in K} z_k \cdot [C_{kin} \cdot ak \cdot (\sum_{i \in I} x_{ik}) + Fk] + \sum_{k \in K} (1 - z_k) \cdot C_{kout} \cdot ak \cdot (\sum_{i \in I} x_{ik})\}$$

Where:

- $(C_{Pik} + C_{Tik}) \cdot x_{ik}$: cost of purchasing and transporting residue k from supplier i .
- $z_k \cdot [C_{kin} \cdot ak \cdot (\sum_{i \in I} x_{ik}) + Fk]$: cost of internal transformation, including both variable and fixed costs, if the internal treatment facility for residue k is activated.
- $(1 - z_k) \cdot C_{kout} \cdot ak \cdot (\sum_{i \in I} x_{ik})$: cost incurred when outsourcing the transformation process

for residue k . For simplicity, this also includes the cost of transporting the transformed material back to the utiliser.

2.2.3 Model constraints

1. Demand constraint for residue type k :

$$\sum_{i \in I} x_{ik} \leq dk \quad \forall k \in K$$

The total quantity of residue type k acquired from all suppliers must not exceed the user's total demand. This constraint allows for the possibility that only a portion of the demand is met through the symbiotic relationship, with the remainder potentially covered by virgin raw materials (if applicable).

2. Supply constraint or maximum availability of residue k from supplier i :

$$x_{ik} \leq q_{ik}, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, I\}, k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$$

Each supplier i can offer only a limited quantity of residue type k . This constraint ensures that the utiliser cannot procure more than the amount made available by each supplier, acknowledging that these suppliers may serve multiple clients.

3. Internal treatment capacity constraint:

$$\sum_{i \in I} \alpha_{ik} \cdot x_{ik} \leq cap_k \cdot z_k \quad \forall k \in K$$

If the internal treatment facility for residue k is activated ($z_k = 1$), the amount to be treated (i.e., a fraction α_{ik} of the purchased quantity) must not exceed the facility's maximum capacity. If the facility is not activated ($z_k = 0$), the constraint is effectively null.

4. Non-negativity and binary conditions:

$$x_{ik} \geq 0 \text{ e } z_k \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall i, k$$

Quantities purchased cannot be negative, and the variable z_k is binary.

2.2.4 Model assumptions

To ensure analytical robustness and practicality, the model is based on a series of simplifying assumptions. While these assumptions may reduce the realism of certain scenarios, they enable a clear and interpretable optimisation framework to be established. The main assumptions are as follows:

Known and constant demand: the utiliser's demand for each type of residue is assumed to be known in advance and not to vary over time. Uncertainty or fluctuations in input requirements are not considered in this model version.

- Perfect substitutability of residues: residues are assumed to be fully replaceable with virgin raw materials without any reduction in product quality or performance. In other words, using waste materials is considered functionally equivalent to using traditional inputs.
- Constant unit prices: costs are treated as fixed per unit. The market price fluctuations and volume-based pricing schemes are not considered.

- Rigid processing capacity: internal treatment facilities are modelled with fixed maximum capacities. The possibility of investing in modular or scalable infrastructure is not considered.
- Deterministic setting: the model does not include stochastic variables. All parameters (e.g. availability, costs and capacities) are considered to be fully known and deterministic at the time of decision-making.

2.2.5 Model utility

In summary, the utiliser company compares the procurement costs of traditional raw materials with those associated with industrial symbiosis. Through the proposed model, the company evaluates the economic convenience of IS by considering purchase, transportation, treatment, and facility activation costs. The goal is to identify an optimal trade-off between purchasing, transforming, and transporting residues, so as to minimise the total cost associated with the symbiotic configuration. It is a concrete decision-making tool to support companies interested in initiating or consolidating industrial symbiosis practices by being able to carry out an ex-ante analysis of the costs associated with the procurement of secondary raw materials versus the use of virgin feedstocks. Thus, it is a model that is distinguished by fundamental characteristics such as:

1. Ability to represent realistic configurations, acknowledging that it is often difficult to meet production input needs entirely through residues. Therefore, the model allows for hybrid solutions that combine residues and virgin materials;
2. Capacity to evaluate multiple combinations of suppliers and residue types, enabling the selection of the most economically advantageous sourcing strategy;
3. Distinction between internal or external processing, weighing up the choice of investing in one's own facilities or outsourcing the operation.

In essence, the model is flexible and can be easily adapted to a variety of production contexts and industrial sectors. It is well-suited for integration into the digital platform developed within the GRIP project, thus making IS cost analysis more accessible to small and medium-sized enterprises, which often struggle to assess the potential benefits of such collaborations on their own. From this perspective, the model fosters inter-firm connections within the territorial context of the NODES project.

2.3 Application of the model: case study Vegea

The mathematical model was validated with the application to a real-world case study, Vegea, a company operating in the bio-based materials sector and recipient of cascade funding under the NODES initiative. Vegea is considered a IS practical case as a user and transformer of agro-industrial waste – specifically, dried grape marc (vinaccia) and grape-seed oil – to produce

technical coated fabrics and biomaterials for fashion, furniture and automotive. The aim of this case study was to assess whether the optimisation model could support Vegea in evaluating alternative sourcing configurations for these residues, and in doing so, identify more cost-effective strategies for procurement, transportation and processing. The test involved both a base scenario, mirroring the company's present sourcing strategy, and a series of alternative scenarios simulating potential market or supply variations (e.g. price changes, new suppliers entering the market and changes in treatment strategies). By feeding Vegea's operational data into the model – collected through a dedicated survey sheet – it was able to make optimal decisions in terms of:

- The quantity purchased of each residue from the available suppliers;
- The choice between internal and external treatment;
- The total cost minimisation within the confines of predefined technical and economic constraints.

The following paragraphs will present only the results obtained from the base scenario. While the full model validation requires further data, the base scenario has already proven valuable for testing the functionality of the mathematical optimisation framework using real company data. This initial application underscores the model's potential as a decision-support tool for assessing the economic feasibility of IS configurations.

2.3.1 Company overview – Vegea

Vegea is an Italian bio-based materials company founded in Milan specialised in the transformation of agro-industrial waste – specifically grape – into leather-like technical fabrics. Its technology uses grape-seed oil and dried marc as raw materials to produce a versatile biopolymer. They have a wide market, targeting the sectors as fashion, furniture, packaging and automotive. Vegea acts as a user and transformer in the IS relationship: it acquires grape marc from wineries, treats it internally to produce bio-textiles and thereby closes the production loop within the region ecosystem. In its actual operational setup, Vegea sources two types of agro-industrial residues: dried grape marc and grape seed oil from two main suppliers located in Northern Italy. These are purchased and processed to serve as key feedstocks in the company production chain. The dried grape marc is a waste and thereby fully treated internally through a steam explosion process to extract cellulous and lignin for bio-based polymer. Instead, grape seed oil is a by-product used directly in chemical transformation steps without preliminary treatment. The company's current sourcing strategy reflects a balance between cost efficiency and long-term supplier reliability. Figure 9 summarises the variables of this configuration. Vegea's annual demand for dried grape marc is about 4.500 kg. The 100% of the purchased residue must undergo treatment before utilisation. This treatment is carried out internally with a variable cost of €0.05/kg, in addition to a fixed daily activation cost of €150. The treatment facility operates with a maximum capacity of 500 kg/day, processed in 10 separate lots of 50 kg each. For the grape-

seed oil, Vegea requires an annual quantity of 10.500 kg. This residue does not require any preliminary treatment and therefore no variable or fixed costs relating to the transformation are chargeable.

	Producer 1		Producer 2	
Distance (km.)	97		340	
	RP1	RP2	RP1	RP2
Price	0.05	4	0.05	4
Transp.cost	0.194	0.291	0.68	1.02
Total supply	??	??	??	??

	RP1	RP2
Inter.treat.cost	0.05	-
Fixed treat.cost	150/day	-
Share to be treated	100%	0%

Figure 9. Current Vegea's sourcing setup

2.3.2 Application of the model to the base scenario

In the base scenario, the optimisation model simulates Vegea's current sourcing strategy by assigning the full available supply from each producer to meet the user's demand. In other words, 3.000 kg of dried grape marc (RP1) and 7.000 kg of grape seed oil (RP2) are sourced from supplier 1, while 1.500 kg of RP1 and 3.500 of Rp2 are purchased from supplier 2. The total annual cost for Vegea under this configuration – including purchase, transport and internal treatment – is €63.159.

Figure 10. Optimised Allocation of residues across the suppliers.

This scenario provides a benchmark for future evaluations. The model application is useful for showing the idea, but it presents some limitations related to data availability. First of all, the model suggests that the total amount of RP1 could be treated internally in just 9 working days, assuming full daily capacity. However, the company indicated that treatment activities are strategically distributed throughout the year, depending on production needs, underscoring a discrepancy between theoretical efficiency and practical operations. Secondly, no data about the cost of outsourcing treatment process were available, precluding a comparison between internal and external transformation strategies. Thirdly, the present version of the model incorporated merely two suppliers, corresponding to Vegea's current partners, and does not explore the potential benefits of expanding the sourcing network to include other residues providers. All these limitations should be considered in future iterations of the model to facilitate more robust consistent decision-making.

2.4 Conclusions

Initially developed to assist companies in determining the feasibility of entering new IS partnership, the model has also proven to be highly valuable for those already engaged in such collaborative relationship. For utiliser companies, such as Vegea, which regularly engage with secondary raw materials, the model can function as a practical instrument to facilitate navigation of the daily market variability as changes in prices, fluctuations in supply or the arrival of new potential suppliers. Indeed, the model enables companies to simulate diverse procurement configurations and compare costs across scenarios, thereby assisting them in making informed decisions when conditions change. In conclusion, the model is not solely for companies entering the IS market for the first time, but it is also a valuable support for those already engaged in these activities.

Part III – COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF IMPLEMENTING IS IN THE NODES AREA

3.1 Overview

The analysis outlined herein aims to assess the economic benefits of IS between potentially complementary companies: on the one hand, the producer of the production residue, and on the other, the utiliser who can employ it as a substitute for virgin raw materials. The main objective is to understand whether the possible symbiotic collaboration generates a net economic benefit for the producer-utiliser system, considering both the additional costs (processing, transport and process adaptation) and the achievable savings (disposal, supply, monetizable environmental benefits). To meet this necessity, the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) methodology was adopted, as it is considered the most suitable for providing a comprehensive and comparable assessment of the economic and environmental impacts generated by an IS project. Unlike other economic evaluation methodologies, such as cost-effectiveness analysis or cost-utility analysis, CBA allows all costs and benefits to be translated into monetary terms, including environmental costs and benefits assessed using indirect evaluation techniques such as shadow pricing. This feature provides a summary indicator of cost-effectiveness, i.e. the net present value (NPV), which is a useful tool for comparing two or more alternative scenarios (e.g. business-as-usual and the symbiotic scenario) and for assessing the net delta of benefits for all parties involved. Therefore, CBA is based on a principle of allocative efficiency that allows alternative scenarios to be compared, considering the new configuration of exchange between companies that improves the overall use of economic and environmental resources. This completeness of information, which also includes positive and negative externalities, makes CBA particularly suitable for valuing projects of this type, providing robust support for political, industrial or land-use planning decisions and enabling integrated quantification of medium- to long-term impacts. The use of CBA is in line with international recommendations (IPCC, UNFCCC) for the assessment of complex environmental projects, even in the presence of uncertainty. The approach adopted in this study considers the variability of transport costs, processing technologies, distances between companies, current regulations and externalities, including scenarios sensitive to uncertainty and applying time discounting criteria for evaluation over time.

3.2 Reference Framework

The cost-benefit analysis developed as part of this project is based on a framework inspired by the theoretical model presented in the work of Yazan & Fraccascia (2020), which combines an Enterprise Input-Output (EIO) approach with an agent-based simulation to examine the operational and economic conditions of IS. Although this work does not implement the agent-

based component, the EIO model proposed in the study forms the conceptual and structural basis of the analysis. The EIO model is particularly effective in representing the interactions between companies operating in a collaborative symbiosis, as it allows:

- (1) Modelling the physical and monetary flows between the producer (company α) and the user (company β);
- (2) Quantify the waste management costs of company α and the procurement costs of company β ;
- (3) Assess the economic impact of replacing virgin raw materials with production residues from other companies;
- (4) Include additional cooperation costs, such as transport and any waste treatment.

In this context, the model has been simplified and adapted for use in an aggregate analysis that considers the entire symbiotic system (i.e. $\alpha + \beta$) and compares the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario with the scenario in which IS is implemented. The adoption of this framework allows quantitative assessments to be made based on technical data and realistic economic assumptions, making the analysis transparent and replicable. In addition to this, environmental benefits have also been included in the model in monetary form, through the shadow pricing of avoided emissions, thus offering an integrated view of the impacts generated by the symbiosis system.

3.3 Model formulation

The model used to assess the operational sustainability of the symbiotic relationship focuses on two main actors:

- (1) Company α , which produces a main output and generates a residual (w_α);
- (2) Company β , which uses the residual from α as a secondary input alternative to a virgin raw material (r_β).

Considering two production processes owned by two companies, for simplicity's sake, it was assumed that each process produces a main output, whereby α generates a single type of waste and β requires a single production input. The amount of waste produced by α (i.e. w_α) and the amount of primary input required by β (i.e. r_β) depend on the amount of main outputs produced by these companies (triggered by market demand) as well as on the production technology. The physical flows described above are summarised in Figure 11. The relationships between the physical flows are expressed of the product between the quantity produced by the companies and their technical coefficients. The lower the values of W_α and R_β (technical coefficients representative of production technologies), the more technically efficient and environmentally friendly the production processes adopted are. Valued of x^α , x^β , W^α , and R^β can change over time.

Producer α	Utiliser β
$w^\alpha = W^\alpha x^\alpha$	$r^\beta = R^\beta x^\beta$
<p>w^α = quantity of waste produced. W^α = waste production rate, based on how many units of waste are generated α per unit of main production. x^α = quantity of main outputs produced.</p>	<p>r^β = primary input required. R^β = input consumption rate, how many primary input units are required by β per main production unit. x^β = quantity of the main outputs produced.</p>

Figure 11. Production process of companies α and β

Changes in x^α and x^β can be triggered by market demand for the main products of α and β , respectively, while changes in W^α and R^β are possible thanks to technological innovation. In this regard, if α improves its production process in order to reduce the rate of waste production, the value of W^α is reduced. Similarly, if β improves its production process in such a way as to reduce the rate of input consumption, the value of R^β is reduced. This CBA analysis is based on a comparison between two scenarios:

(1) Scenario 1 - Business as usual (BAU)

This baseline scenario represents current practices, in which α disposes of its waste through traditional channels (landfill or incineration), incurring associated costs (transport and disposal). β sources virgin raw materials on the market, without using secondary resources, incurring purchase and transport costs from the local supplier.

(2) Scenario 2 – IS implementation

In this scenario, we must consider the material flows exchanged between the two companies. There are three possibilities:

a. $w^\alpha = r^\beta$

α 's waste streams fully meet β 's raw material requirements. α 's waste is completely removed from disposal, avoiding disposal costs and replacing β 's raw material. This scenario maximises economic and environmental benefits, but the costs of cooperation take precedence.

b. $w^\alpha < r^\beta$

α 's waste streams do not fully meet β 's raw material demand, which will have a mix of virgin resources (with associated purchase costs) and secondary raw materials from α .

c. $w^\alpha > r^\beta$

α 's waste streams fully meet β 's excess demand, so α still bears the disposal costs while β has raw materials that are entirely driven by symbiotic relationships.

3.3.1 Scenario BAU

No symbiotic relationship occurs, so α discharges w^α units of waste to the landfill and β purchases r^β units of primary input from one or more conventional suppliers. BAU costs are calculated as follows:

Table 15. Computation of BAU costs.

Disposal costs for α	$C_{w^\alpha} = (C_{w^\alpha}^l + C_{w^\alpha}^{al}) \times w^\alpha$	$C_{w^\alpha}^l$ = disposal cost per unit for w^α $C_{w^\alpha}^{al}$ = transport cost of one unit of w^α from α to the landfill site
Purchasing costs β	$C_{r^\beta} = (C_{r^\beta}^s + C_{r^\beta}^{s\beta}) \times r^\beta$	$C_{r^\beta}^s$ = cost of purchasing one unit of r^β from conventional supplier s $C_{r^\beta}^{s\beta}$ = cost of transporting one unit of r^β from s to β .
Total BAU costs	$C_{BAU} = C_{w^\alpha} + C_{r^\beta}$	Sum of α and β costs.

The costs of α depend on several factors, e.g. market prices for disposal, distance between the company and the landfill site, market prices for transport services, waste disposal regulations. The cost of β can be influenced by, for example, market prices for primary resources, transport distance between the company and the supplier, market prices for transport services.

3.3.2 Scenario of Symbiotic relationship

The waste generated by α is used to replace the primary input required by β . In this case, waste disposal costs and input purchase costs are reduced. However, the economic benefits are eaten up by the extra costs needed to manage the relationship with the IS, in particular transport and waste treatment costs (costs to make the waste available for use as input). Depending on the different amount of w^α produced and r^β required, three situations can occur (Table 16):

Table 16. The three possible outcomes of the symbiotic scenario.

$w^\alpha = r^\beta$	C^{is}
$w^\alpha > r^\beta$	$C^{is} = C_{w^\alpha r^\beta}^{\alpha\beta} \times r^\beta$ $C_{w^\alpha} = (C_{w^\alpha}^l + C_{w^\alpha}^{al}) \times (w^\alpha - r^\beta)$
$w^\alpha < r^\beta$	$C^{is} = C_{w^\alpha r^\beta}^{\alpha\beta} \times w^\alpha$ $C_{r^\beta} = (C_{r^\beta}^s + C_{r^\beta}^{s\beta}) \times (r^\beta - w^\alpha)$

- **Perfect match** – In the first set of circumstances, there is a perfect match between the amount of waste produced and the amount of inputs required. α does not discharge any waste units, and β does not purchase any input units from the conventional supplier. Only the IS cost occurs.
- **Waste surplus** – In the second case, the total amount of input is replaced by waste. β

does not purchase any primary input units from the conventional supplier, while α still disposes of $(w\alpha - r\beta)$ units of waste in landfill. The additional cost of IS relations depends on the total additional cost required to exchange one unit of $r\beta$ between the two companies.

- **Waste deficit** – In the latter case, the total amount of waste is used to replace the primary input. α does not dump any waste, while β still purchases the difference $(r\beta - w\alpha)$ units of primary input from the conventional supplier. The additional cost of IS relations depends on the total additional cost required to exchange one unit of $w\alpha$ between the two companies.

3.3.3 Discount rate and time horizon

In the framework of CBA, the choice of discount rate and time horizon is important to ensure an accurate assessment of the economic flows associated with symbiotic territorial collaboration. This significantly influences the calculation of the Net Present Value (NPV) and, consequently, the perceived economic viability of the project. The discount rate reflects the present value attributed to future flows of costs and benefits. It includes relevant components such as the cost of capital, the risk premium associated with the uncertainty of future flows, and expected inflation. The literature suggests using different discount rates depending on the nature of the project:

- (1) For initiatives of the public interest with significant environmental and social impacts, a relatively low social discount rate (2-3%) is recommended.
- (2) For private projects or those with operational risks, the use of a market rate (5-10%) is more appropriate.

Considering that the following analysis evaluates a collaboration from an IS perspective that involves private entities, presents elements of uncertainty related to the stability of waste flows and treatment costs and generates environmental benefits of collective interest. Therefore, it was decided to adopt a discount rate of 5%, which will help to balance the situations described above. This value will be subject to variation in sensitivity analyses, so that alternative scenarios with lower or higher rates can be explored. In addition, the choice of time horizon must consider several factors, such as:

- (1) The duration of investments, as the infrastructure and technological adaptations required for IS tend to have a rather long useful life.
- (2) The stability of benefits, as economic savings and avoided emissions tend to stabilise in the medium term.
- (3) The uncertainty of constantly evolving markets.

Taking all these aspects into account, we have established a 10-year time horizon for assessing cost and benefit flows. This choice is in line with the guidelines for pilot projects or medium-scale initiatives, which seek to balance a long-term vision with an acceptable level of predictability.

3.3.3.1 Net Present Value (NPV)

Overall efficiency is assessed using NPV, which summarises the economic and environmental benefits over time, discounted at a rate r .

$$NPV = \sum \frac{(Benefits - Costs)}{(1 + r)^t}$$

where the benefits correspond to the costs saved in the BAU scenario (costs avoided for waste disposal and the purchase of raw materials), while other costs arise, i.e. the additional costs for transporting and processing waste, which are shared between the two companies and require agreements or contractual mechanisms to ensure a balanced distribution of costs.

Therefore, the general structure of the formula is as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{[(C_{wa}^l + C_{wa}^{al}) + (C_{r\beta}^s + C_{r\beta}^{s\beta}) - C^{is}] \times w^\alpha}{(1 + r)^t} \quad w^\beta \leq r^\beta \\ \frac{[(C_{wa}^l + C_{wa}^{al}) + (C_{r\beta}^s + C_{r\beta}^{s\beta}) - C^{is}] \times r^\beta}{(1 + r)^t} \quad w^\beta \geq r^\beta \end{array} \right.$$

where the benefits are represented by the savings achieved through the IS project compared to the BAU scenario in which waste is disposed of and raw materials are purchased.

Avoided Costs: $(C_{wa}^l + C_{wa}^{al}) + (C_{r\beta}^s + C_{r\beta}^{s\beta})$

- $C_{w\alpha}^l$ = waste disposal cost per unit of $w\alpha$ for company α
- $C_{w\alpha}^{al}$ = transport cost per unit of $w\alpha$ a disposal site
- $C_{r\beta}^{s\beta}$ = transport cost per unit of $r\beta$ from suppliers
- $C_{r\beta}^s$ = purchase cost per unit of $r\beta$ for company β

On the other hand, symbiosis costs are the additional costs incurred to enable IS.

Therefore:

- Waste transport costs (from α to β);
- Waste processing or treatment costs to make it exploitable;
- Administrative or regulatory costs (e.g. permits, coordination).

Case 1: $w^\alpha \leq r^\beta$

$$\frac{[(C_{wa}^l + C_{wa}^{al}) + (C_{r\beta}^s + C_{r\beta}^{s\beta}) - C^{is}] \times w^\alpha}{(1+r)^t}$$

In this case, all waste is used by the raw material user. The benefits are calculated based on the amount of waste delivered. The avoided costs and IS costs are scaled relative to w^α .

Case 2: $w^\alpha \geq r^\beta$

$$\frac{[(C_{wa}^l + C_{wa}^{al}) + (C_{r\beta}^s + C_{r\beta}^{s\beta}) - C^{is}] \times r^\beta}{(1+r)^t}$$

Only the demand for raw materials is met by waste; any excess waste is disposed of. The benefits are calculated based on the quantity of raw material replaced. The avoided costs and IS costs are scaled with respect to r^β .

3.3.4 Allocation of additional symbiosis costs

Allocation of additional costs related to symbiosis The realisation of an IS project also involves a series of additional operating costs related to the waste transport and processing. Therefore, a key factor in the economic feasibility of symbiotic collaboration is the allocation of these costs between company α and company β . To model this allocation, a cost-sharing parameter indicated by lambda (λ) is introduced, which represents the share of additional costs incurred by company α . On the other hand, β incurs a share equal to $(1-\lambda)$. In the following, the general formulas for the individual companies are based on the match between the waste and the necessary raw material:

$$\Delta_\alpha = \begin{cases} (C_{w^\alpha}^l + C_{w^\alpha}^{al}) \times w^\alpha - \lambda \times C_{w^\alpha r^\beta}^{\alpha\beta} \times w^\alpha & \text{if } w^\beta \leq r^\beta \\ (C_{w^\alpha}^l + C_{w^\alpha}^{al}) \times r^\beta - \lambda \times C_{w^\alpha r^\beta}^{\alpha\beta} \times r^\beta & \text{if } w^\beta \geq r^\beta \end{cases}$$

$$\Delta_\beta = \begin{cases} (C_{w^\alpha}^l + C_{w^\alpha}^{al}) \times w^\alpha - (1-\lambda) \times C_{w^\alpha r^\beta}^{\alpha\beta} \times w^\alpha & \text{if } w^\beta \leq r^\beta \\ (C_{w^\alpha}^l + C_{w^\alpha}^{al}) \times r^\beta - (1-\lambda) \times C_{w^\alpha r^\beta}^{\alpha\beta} \times r^\beta & \text{if } w^\beta \geq r^\beta \end{cases}$$

In which the benefits linked to the avoided costs of the BAU scenario are subtracted from the costs arising from the symbiotic relationship. Depending on the value assumed by λ , different collaboration scenarios can be identified:

- **$\lambda = 1$:** the producer α bears the full additional costs. This may occur if α has a primary interest in avoiding disposal costs.
- **$\lambda = 0$:** the user company β bears the entire costs. This occurs if β attaches high economic value to the by-product received.
- **$0 < \lambda < 1$:** the costs are shared between α and β according to fair cooperation agreements.

- $\lambda > 1$: α : not only covers all costs, but also offers β a monetary incentive for using its waste (e.g. less desirable or difficult to treat waste).
- $\lambda < 0$: β : purchases the waste from α , paying for it in addition to the operating costs of the symbiosis, in the case of high-value residues.

This modelling allows us to analyse the impact of cost sharing on the economic convenience of the parties. For company α , the benefit mainly depends on the savings in disposal costs compared to the additional transport and treatment costs it has to bear. For company β , the benefit comes from savings in the purchase costs of virgin raw materials, net of the costs associated with the processing and management of secondary materials. The symbiosis will only be acceptable to both parties if each one records a positive net benefit compared to the BAU scenario. Therefore, the determination of λ must reflect the bargaining power of the companies, the quality and desirability of the residue, and the alternatives available for disposal or procurement. The analysis conducted allows us to identify the ranges of λ within which symbiosis is economically advantageous for both companies, supporting the definition of balanced and sustainable cooperation agreements over time.

3.3.5 Emissions calculation

IS can generate significant environmental benefits, particularly through the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. These benefits derive from two main mechanisms:

1. **Avoided disposal of production residues in landfills:** company α does not transport its waste to landfills, thus avoiding the emissions associated with these operations.
2. **Replacement of virgin raw materials:** company β uses α 's residues as production inputs, avoiding the emissions associated with the extraction, processing and transport of the raw materials replaced.

To include these environmental benefits in the cost-benefit analysis, they are monetised through the application of carbon shadow pricing, based on the market value (or social reference value) of the avoided emissions. The total value of avoided emissions (ACO_2) is calculated as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_{CO_2} = \frac{(E_{wa} \times w^\alpha + E_{r\beta} \times w^\alpha) \times CP}{(1+r)^t} \quad w^\beta \leq r^\beta \\ A_{CO_2} = \frac{(E_{wa} \times r^\beta + E_{r\beta} \times r^\beta) \times CP}{(1+r)^t} \quad w^\beta \geq r^\beta \end{array} \right.$$

Where:

- (1) $E_{w\alpha}$ = avoided emissions per tonne of waste diverted from disposal (kgCO₂e/ton);
- (2) $E_{r\beta}$ = emissions avoided per tonne of raw material replaced (kg CO₂e/ton);

(3) CP = carbon price (€/tonne CO₂e), defined according to the reference values of the regulated EU ETS markets.

The calculation distinguishes between two cases::

- **Case 1: $w\alpha \leq r\beta$**
All waste produced by α is used by β . The avoided emissions are calculated on the basis of $w\alpha$.
- **Case 2: $w\alpha \geq r\beta$**
Only part of the waste is used by β . The avoided emissions are calculated on the basis of $r\beta$.

Ultimately, the economic value of avoided emissions is included in the CBA balance sheet as an environmental monetary benefit, contributing to an increase in the NPV of the project.

3.4 Model Assumptions

This analysis is built on a set of basic assumptions that help to simplify the operational reality, making the model both transparent and applicable. It's important to note that these assumptions aren't meant to cover every possible scenario; rather, they serve as a reference point for consistently evaluating the IS benefits. The first point concerns the stability of production flows: it is assumed that the quantity of residues generated by the manufacturing company and the raw material needs of the user company remain relatively constant during the analysis period. Any market fluctuations are not included in the baseline scenario but are explored through simulations and sensitivity analyses. It is also assumed that the residues can fully replace the virgin raw materials used by company β without compromising the final quality of the product. Any treatments necessary to ensure the suitability of the material are already accounted for in the processing costs. On the economic side, the analysis looks at average and stable unit prices for the main cost items (transport, disposal, treatment, purchase of raw materials). By neutralising market dynamics, it has been created a clear comparison between the traditional scenario and the symbiotic scenario, leaving sensitivity analyses to understand the impact of possible variations. The technological capabilities of treatment plants are treated as fixed, without considering modular increases or new innovations over the time horizon. In this way, the focus remains on currently feasible configurations, while future technological developments are viewed as alternative scenarios. The model operates in a deterministic environment, where quantities, costs and distances are known and certain. Uncertainty is addressed at a later stage, by introducing variation scenarios or probabilistic simulations to return a more realistic range of results. A key aspect is the allocation of the additional costs of symbiosis (transport, treatment, coordination), modelled using a sharing parameter (λ). This coefficient summarises the different contractual balance between companies: different values of λ allow us to explore situations in which the costs fall more on the producer, more on the user, or are shared equally. A constant

discount rate of 5% is used to discount cash flows over the entire ten-year horizon. This choice reflects the mixed nature of the analysis: on the one hand, it is a collaboration between private entities, while on the other hand, the environmental benefits generated have a collective value that suggests the adoption of an intermediate rate. Finally, the environmental benefits linked to avoided emissions are included in the analysis through the shadow price monetisation of carbon. The price of carbon is considered constant over the reference period, while recognising that an upward trend would provide a further incentive for symbiosis.

These assumptions, while simplifying the real complexity, allow us to outline a clear and coherent picture of the economic benefits of IS and provide a useful tool for businesses and public decision-makers to guide strategic choices.

3.5 Application of the CBA model at the NODES scale

After describing the theoretical framework, this section describes in detail the operational process followed to develop the cost-benefit analysis applied to the IS evaluation in the NODES territory. The methodological steps adopted are documented, from the selection of companies to the construction of the scenarios analysed, highlighting the data sources used, the operational assumptions made, and the calculation techniques applied. The process was divided into several sequential steps: identification of companies potentially involved in symbiosis, collection and estimation of technical and economic data, modelling of BAU and symbiosis scenarios, calculation of environmental benefits, and analysis of economic convenience using NPV. All the steps that led to the development of the analysis are described systematically below.

3.5.1 Definition of symbiotic flows and identification of potentially involved companies

The first step in the analysis was to identify potential IS relationships applicable to the NODES territory. To this end, reference was made to the results obtained in the RM1 research module. The decision to test the model on the RM1 matrices was based on the greater reliability and availability of data relating to these flows: RM1 presents industrial applications that provide more reliable values, thus ensuring greater robustness of the simulations and results obtained. In the future, application to other research modules is not ruled out, but this step was necessary to validate the approach on already established industrial cases. The full matrix of RM1 showing the combinations of production sectors that are compatible in terms of production and use of by-products can be found in Deliverable 6.4 Part II. Basing on such matrix, a list of ATECO codes was drawn up representing the economic activities potentially involved, both as waste producers (company α) and as users (company β). The list of ATECO codes (Table 17) included sectors belonging to the extractive industry, the production of construction materials, waste management, and other related sectors.

Table 17. Ateco codes considered in RM1

ATECO codes	Activities
08.11.00	Extraction of ornamental and building stone, limestone, gypsum, clay and slate
08.12.00	Extraction of gravel and sand; extraction of clays and kaolin
08.09.09	Extraction of other minerals from quarries and mines
23.20.00	Manufacture of refractory products
23.31.00	Manufacture of ceramic tiles for flooring and cladding
23.42.00	Manufacture of ceramic sanitary ware
23.51.00	Production of cement
23.61.00	Manufacture of concrete products for construction
23.64.00	Production of mortar
23.69.00	Manufacture of other concrete, plaster and cement products
38.11.00	Collection of non-hazardous waste
38.21.09	Treatment and disposal of other non-hazardous waste
39.00.09	Other remediation activities and other waste management services
43.11.00	Demolition

Starting from this set of codes, a selection of companies was made using the database of companies located in the reference territory (Piedmont and the Lombardy provinces of Pavia, Como, and Varese). All companies that had one of the identified ATECO codes as their primary or secondary code were considered. The selection process resulted in 71 out of 651 companies in Lombardy being found compatible with the project. In Piedmont, on the other hand, 140 out of 1,112 companies had activities consistent with the symbiotic exchanges identified. These companies were then geolocated using GIS software to enable spatial analysis related to the logistics of material flows and the calculation of transport costs.

3.5.2 Territorial mapping

After selecting the companies potentially involved in symbiotic relationships, we proceeded with their geographical mapping using Geographic Information System (GIS) tools. This allowed us to pinpoint the territorial distribution of companies within the boundaries of the NODES project

(with additional support from Google Maps in cases where geolocation was not possible). It also allowed for a realistic estimate of the distances between waste producers (α), potential users (β), and disposal facilities in the area, which then enabled the calculation of transport costs associated with the different scenarios. In the GIS map, the following were included:

- The geolocated points of the selected companies, classified according to their sector (Figure 12). The addresses of NODES companies were obtained from information provided by the local Chamber of Commerce. Only one company could not be geolocated using QGIS or Google Maps (the company in question is SPURGO*JET - S.R.L., based in Piedmont).
- The location of the main active waste disposal facilities in the NODES area (Figure 13). The addresses of these facilities were drawn up by cross-referencing information available on the ARPA Piemonte and ISPRA websites. In total, there are 21 landfill sites in Piedmont and 5 sites spread across the provinces of Como, Varese, and Pavia. Based on the type of waste treated, only landfill sites dealing with hazardous, non-hazardous, and inert special waste were selected.
- After mapping these points, a vector of roads accessible to trucks (the assumed means of transport for waste) was added (Figure 14), obtained from regional OpenStreetMap data provided by Geofabrik. This vector allowed, also through the use of the QGIS Network Analysis Toolbox 3 (QNEAT3) plug-in, to visualise the roads that could be travelled by the selected Piedmonts and Lombard companies to the special waste landfills, thus estimating an average distance to be used in the cost-benefit analysis. This data was also used as a proxy to assess the distance between the suppliers of virgin raw materials and the β companies (as it is not possible to know their precise location).

Figure 12. Mapping companies within the NODES territory.

Figure 13. Mapping Special waste Landfills within the NODES territory

Figure 14. Roads accessible by companies to landfills.

With the help of the vector analysis tools created, QGIS returned the statistics presented in Table 18.

Table 18. Main statistics obtained by the mapping.

Statistics	Value	Description
Total number of connections	5.407	Number of lines (company → landfill)
Unique values	4.823	There are some repetitions
Null values	53	53 invalid connections (no route found)
Minimum distance	911 m	The closest company-landfill
Maximum distance	286 km	Farthest company-landfill
Mean	94.651 m	Approximately 95 km on average between company and landfill
Median	94.054 m	Very close to the mean, therefore balanced distribution
1st Quartile (Q1)	59.344 m	25% of companies travel less than 59 km
3rd Quartile (Q3)	126.034 m	75% travel less than 126 km
IQR (Q3 - Q1)	66.690 m	Interquartile variability

Standard deviation	46.982 m	Interquartile variability
Coefficient of variation	0.50	Scattered data, but acceptable

The maximum range is high, but most companies are located less than 130 km from the landfill. Approximately 5% of connections could not be found (53 out of 5,407). It is assumed that this percentage of unlocated connections is due to inaccurate coordinates.

3.5.3 Technical and economic data collection

Once the territorial point of reference had been defined, the technical and economic data necessary for the cost-benefit analysis were collected. Where data were missing or not directly available for the Italian context, prudent estimates were made on the basis of international literature, always documenting the sources used. In this sense, a complete and structured dataset was constructed, necessary to feed the cost and benefit calculation models in both scenarios considered. For each symbiotic flow identified, the following parameters were collected or estimated:

- (1) **Waste Generation Rate (W_{α}).** This quantifies the amount of waste produced by company α for each unit of output. The values were obtained from the available scientific literature, integrating specific sources on the industrial sectors considered. For some matrices, it was not possible to find any reference data.
- (2) **Input Consumption Rate (R_{β}).** Indicates the quantity of secondary material required by company β per unit of output. These data were also obtained from bibliographic sources and technical reports in the sector.
- (3) **Residue treatment costs.** Estimates of the cost required to make the residue suitable for reuse. Data were obtained from sector price lists, technical reports, and scientific articles, adapting them to the Italian context where possible.
- (4) **Traditional disposal costs.** Average prices charged for landfill disposal based on the type of waste.
- (5) **Purchase costs of virgin raw materials.** Average market prices for the raw materials that the secondary material would replace.
- (6) **Transport costs.** Computed based on average kilometres costs for road freight transport of loads exceeding 26 tons, updated in June 2024 according to the rates published by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport (link). The mean cost used was €2.5405/km for a fully loaded truck, normalized on a ton-kilometres basis (€/ton-km), resulting in approximately 0.0977/ton-km.

Table 19. Sources related to waste production rates.

N	Matrix	Waste generation rate	Source
1.1.	Fine mineral waste	10-35%	(Manning & Vetterlein, 2004)
		10-30%	(Clive Mitchell, 2009)
		12-60%	(Rodrigues et al., 2013)
1.2.	Bottom Ash	20-35%	(Schabbach et al., 2012)
1.3.	Fly ash	3-10%	(Kanhar et al., 2020)
1.4.			
1.5.	Fired ceramic waste	15-30%	(Chang et al., 2023b)
1.6.	Industrial mineral waste	51%	(Tazzini et al., 2024)
		39-53%	(Hamza et al., 2011)
1.7.	Coarse mineral waste	20-63% (CDW)	(Zhang et al., 2020)
		no data (quarry activities)	(Ossa et al., 2016)
1.8.	Silicate rock quarry waste	no data	

Table 20. Sources related to input consumption rates (or recovery rates)

N	Symbiosis output	Input consumption rate or material recovery rate	Sources
1.1.	Technosoil	60-100%	(Azevedo-Lopes et al., 2024)
		60%	(Yilmaz et al., 2017)
1.2.	Ceramic products and high-value cementitious materials	60%	(Schabbach et al., 2012)
1.3.	Geopolymers for ceramic products	35-45%	(Silva et al., 2017)
1.4.	Metal recovery	85-90%	(Izumikawa, 1996)

1.5.	Ceramic products	40%	(Planelles-Aragó et al., s.d.)
		80-100%	(Fugazzotto et al., 2023)
1.6.	Technosoil	60-100%	(Azevedo-Lopes et al., 2024)
		60%	(Yilmaz et al., 2017)
1.7.	Certifiable aggregates	10-40%	(Ossa et al., 2016)
		20-40%	(Khamis et al., 2024)
1.8.	Feeding material for REE enrichment	20-50%	(Pyrgaki et al., 2021)

Table 21. Sources related to the costs of treating product matrices

N	Waste	Treatment cost (€/ton)	Treatment required
1.1.	Fine mineral waste	10,00 €	Mixing of aggregates with organic by-products
1.2.	Bottom ash	<u>200,00 €</u>	High-temperature inertisation with geopolymer formation
1.3.	Fly ash	<u>20,00 €</u>	Reduction of PTE through leaching cycles and subsequent recovery of leached metals
1.4.			
1.5.	Fired ceramic waste	15,00 €	Grinding to different particle sizes, blending of different types of ceramic waste
1.6.	Industrial mineral waste	<u>25,00 €</u>	Crushing and screening to obtain grain sizes suitable for base material. Fine fraction, added to soil and organic component for the production of technosoil
1.7.	Coarse mineral waste	<u>50,00 €</u>	Upstream treatment of heterogeneous waste materials: crushing, screening, magnetic separation, possible pneumatic separation for fine elements. Selection of materials constituting mixes for the production of reinforced earth for civil and infrastructure works
1.8.	Silicate rock quarry waste	no data	Search for the presence of CRM in mining waste, focus on REE (separation treatment up to mineral concentrate)

Table 22. Sources related to special waste disposal costs

N	Waste	Disposal cost (€/ton)	Source
1.1.	Fine mineral waste	24,00 € (quarry)	link
		390,00 € (CDW)	link
1.2.	Bottom ash	50,00 €	Link
1.3.	Fly ash	50,00 €	Link
1.4.			
1.5.	Fired ceramic waste	18,00 €	link
1.6.	Industrial mineral waste	24,00 €	link
1.7.	Coarse mineral waste	390,00 € (CDW)	link
		24,00 € (quarry)	link
1.8.	Silicate rock quarry waste	24,00 €	link

Table 23. Sources related to the purchase costs of virgin raw materials

N	Symbiosis output	Virgin raw material	Price of VRM	Source
1.1.	Technosoil	Natural soil	10,00 €	Prezzario Regione Piemonte
1.2.	Ceramic products and high-value cementitious materials	Natural cementitious material	150,00 €	Prezzario Biella
1.3.	Geopolymers for ceramic products	Natural cementitious material	150,00 €	Prezzario Biella
1.4.	Metal recovery	Virgin metal from extraction	200,00 €	Quotazione metalli
1.5.	Ceramic products	Natural cementitious and ceramic material (quartz and feldspar)	50,00 €	Prezzario Regione Piemonte
1.6.	Technosoil	Natural soil	no data	

1.7.	Certifiable aggregates	Natural aggregates	15,00 €	<u>Inerti</u>
1.8.	Feeding material for REE enrichment	Use of mineral resources	no data	

3.5.4 Estimate of production scale using Monte Carlo simulation

One of the key elements in assessing the economic viability of IS is the production scale of the companies involved, i.e. the annual volume of residues produced by company α and the input requirements of company β . However, these data on the annual production volume of individual companies were not directly available. To overcome this limitation, a Monte Carlo simulation was implemented to estimate the production levels of the companies in a plausible manner, thus introducing variability and uncertainty into the assessment while reflecting the real diversity of the production fabric. The procedure adopted was as follows:

1. Average production per employee

For each ATECO code involved (08, 23, 38), the average annual production per employee was calculated by dividing national production in tonnes (Produzione in valore e quantità per tutti i prodotti (Prodcom), s.d.) by the number of employees in the sector at national level. For codes 39 and 43, it was not possible to proceed due to the absence of useful data (as services or data were obscured). In order not to exclude these categories from the analysis, it was decided to extend the production ranges calculated for ATECO codes that are similar from a technological/sectoral point of view, assuming that companies of the same size, even if operating in different fields, may have similar dynamics in terms of material generation and reuse (this is a precautionary simplification, taken in order to ensure the continuity of the simulation).

2. Company size

Based on the European classification of enterprises Directive (EU) 2023/2775 issued by the European Commission on 17 October 2023, four size categories were considered (Table 24).

Table 24. Companies classification according to their size.

Company size	Number of employees
Micro	<10
Small	<50
Medium	<250
Large	>250

For the last class, a theoretical maximum of 350 employees was assumed for the purposes of the simulation.

3. Output per size class

Starting from the average production per employee, an annual production range was estimated for each size class by multiplying productivity by the minimum and maximum number of employees. To make the simulation as close as possible to actual production, a variability of $\pm 20\%$ was applied to this range, thus taking into account the heterogeneity of production within each category.

4. Probability distribution

To simulate the production behaviour of companies, different distributions were applied:

- (1) Rectangular distribution for micro, small and medium-sized companies;
- Right-skewed triangular distribution for large companies. This choice takes into account possible economies of scale.

5. Monte Carlo Simulation

Finally, output values were randomly extracted for both actors involved within the estimated ranges, based on the distribution chosen for each type of enterprise. This methodology made it possible to analyse the effect of production scale on the economic convenience of symbiosis and the sustainability of symbiotic practices, even for small enterprises, which are particularly well represented in the territory analysed.

3.5.5 Future scenarios and temporal dynamics

The analysis was based on a comparison between two distinct scenarios: the BAU scenario and the IS scenario. In this light, it was appropriate to consider the evolution of costs and benefits over time, hypothesising four future scenarios:

- (1) Constant scenario. Assumption of unchanged costs and productivity over the 10-year time horizon.
- (2) Inflation scenario. Application of a moderate annual inflation rate (approximately 2%), based on official forecasts (MEF and Bank of Italy).
- (3) Technological innovation scenario. Progressive reduction in waste production ($W\alpha$) and input consumption ($R\beta$) rates, estimated at around 1.5-2% per annum, due to the adoption of more efficient technologies.
- (4) Combined scenario. Simultaneous presence of inflation and technological innovation.

The assumptions regarding the evolution of inflation and technological innovation were formulated on the basis of official sources. The estimates are based on official documents from the Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF) and the Bank of Italy, which forecast a planned inflation rate of around 1.8%–2% per annum for the period 2025–2029. A constant inflation rate of 2% has therefore been assumed for future scenarios, applicable to the main costs of treatment, transport, disposal and procurement of raw materials. Technological innovation in the sectors

analysed (material recovery, waste treatment, use of secondary inputs) can lead both to a reduction in the Waste Generation Rate (W_{α}), thanks to more efficient production processes and more accurate resource management, and to a decrease in the Input Consumption Rate (R_{β}), through improved technologies for the use of secondary materials. The basic assumption is based on ISPRA data on the reduction in the production of special waste in Italy (-1.8% between 2021 and 2022) and the consideration that part of this reduction may be attributable to technological improvements in production processes. Therefore, an annual reduction rate of between 1.5% and 2% has been assumed for the W_{α} and R_{β} parameters, applied prudently, while recognising the uncertainty surrounding the actual evolution of individual sectors.

3.5.6 Calculation of avoided emissions

To estimate the avoided emissions resulting from the implementation of IS in the NODES territory, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) analysis was conducted using the demo version of SimaPro software. The environmental assessment method adopted is Environmental Footprint 3.1 (adapted), developed at European level for the harmonised environmental analysis of products and processes. In line with the theoretical framework outlined in Chapter 2, the focus was placed exclusively on the “Climate Change” impact category, expressed in terms of kg of CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e). This allows for a direct assessment of the climate benefits resulting from both the avoided disposal of waste by manufacturing companies α and the replacement of virgin raw materials by user companies. For each type of waste analysed, a representative dataset for the reference process was identified. In some cases, however, it was not possible to associate the waste or raw material with a dataset that perfectly matched the actual process. In such circumstances, similar processes were used, selected for their technological and functional similarities, in order to maintain the methodological consistency of the analysis. Only for two transformation processes was it not possible to identify a representative dataset in SimaPro. Below, in Table 25, CO₂ emissions for each product matrix. Avoided emissions were calculated according to the following procedure:

- (1) Emissions from avoided disposal. For each type of waste that, in the symbiotic scenario, is not sent to landfill or incineration, the relevant emission factor was applied.
- (2) Emissions from avoided transport. As an alternative to transport to disposal facilities, the avoided emissions per kilometre-tonne not travelled were estimated (in this case, the figure of 0.104 kg CO₂e/t·km was multiplied by the average distance of 95 km in the BAU scenario; in the IS scenario, it was multiplied by the average distance travelled between companies of 100 km).
- (3) Emissions from raw material substitution. For each virgin material substituted, the avoided emissions were estimated using extractive LCA data.

The net environmental benefit was then monetised: the difference between the emissions avoided in the BAU scenario and the new emissions generated by the symbiotic exchange was multiplied by the shadow price of carbon consistent with the average price of EU ETS certificates on the date of calculation (the price was in kg CO₂e per kg, converted to tonnes).

This methodology ensures a transparent and replicable economic assessment of the project, while taking into account the limitations of data availability.

Table 25. CO2 emissions for each matrix.

	Matrix	Components		Emission (kg CO ₂ e/1 Kg)	Emission (kg CO ₂ e/1 ton)	Dataset Ecoinvent
1.1.	Fine waste from CDW, rocks and excavated and quarried earth for the production of technosoil	α avoided emissions	Aggregate landfill (CDW, quarry and excavation rocks)	0,00626	6,26	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, U
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {ReR} Cut-off, U
		β avoided emissions	Natural soil extraction	0,00425	4,25	Sand {RoW} gravel and sand quarry operation Cut-off, U
			Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {ReR}
		Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: Mixing of aggregates with organic by-products	0,00025	0,25	Rock crushing {RER} rock crushing Cut-off, U
			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {ReR}
1.2.	Bottom ash from MSW waste-to-energy plants for the production of high-value ceramic products	α avoided emissions	Landfill site for non-hazardous special waste (bottom ash)	0,00782	7,82	Bottom ash, MSWI-WWT-SLF, municipal solid waste {IT} treatment of bottom ash, MSWI-WWT-SLF, slag compartment Cut-off, U
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}

	and cementitious materials	β avoided emissions	Extraction of virgin material for ceramics	0,00823	8,23	Clay {RoW} clay pit operation Cut-off, U
			Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: high-temperature inertisation process for the formation of geopolymers	2,29	2290	Fly ash and scrubber sludge {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of fly ash and scrubber sludge, hazardous waste incineration Cut-off, U
			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
1.3.	Fly ash from MSW waste-to-energy plants for the creation of geopolymers for ceramic products	α avoided emissions	Landfill site for hazardous special waste (fly ash)	0,34	340	Average incineration residue {RoW} treatment of average incineration residue, residual material landfill Cut-off, U
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		β avoided emissions	Extraction of natural cementitious material	0,0348	34,8	Silica sand {RoW} silica sand production Cut-off, U
			Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: high-temperature inertisation process for the formation of geopolymers	2,29	2290	Fly ash and scrubber sludge {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of fly ash and scrubber sludge, hazardous waste incineration Cut-off, U

			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
1.4.	Fly ash from MSW waste-to-energy plants for metal recovery	α avoided emissions	Landfill site for hazardous special waste (fly ash)	0,34	340	Average incineration residue {RoW} treatment of average incineration residue, residual material landfill Cut-off, U
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		β avoided emissions	Extraction of natural metallic material	0,0131	13,1	Bauxite {GLO} bauxite mine operation Cut-off, U
			Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: Reduction of PTE through leaching cycles	no data	no data	
			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
	Fired ceramic waste for the	α avoided emissions	Landfill for inert waste (ceramic waste)	0,00626	6,26	Treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill RoW
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		β avoided emissions	Extraction of natural cementitious and ceramic materials (quartz and feldspar)	0,0348	34,8	Silica sand {RoW} silica sand production Cut-off, U

1.5.	creation of other ceramic products		Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: Grinding to different grain sizes, blending of different types of ceramic waste	0,018	18	Grinding {RNA} Grinding
			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
	Industrial mineral waste (granite and other carbonaceous)	α avoided emissions	Landfill for inert waste (mineral waste)	0,00626	6,26	Treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill RoW
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		β avoided emissions	Extraction of natural cementitious and ceramic materials (quartz and feldspar)	0,0348	34,8	Silica sand {RoW} silica sand production Cut-off, U
			Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}

1.6.	minerals) used to create technosoil and/or base material for jogging tracks and livestock breeding.	Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: Crushing and screening to obtain suitable grain size classes for base material (jogging tracks). Fine fraction, added to soil and organic component for the production of technosoil	0	0	Clinker {Europe without Switzerland}] clinker production Cut-off, U
			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
1.7.	Coarse mineral waste for the creation of certifiable aggregates	α avoided emissions	Inert waste landfill (mineral waste)	0,00626	6,26	Treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill RoW
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		β avoided emissions	Natural aggregates	0,00423	4,23	Sand {RoW} gravel and sand quarry operation
			Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}

		Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: Upstream treatment of heterogeneous waste materials, followed by crushing, screening, magnetic separation, and possible pneumatic separation for fine elements.	0,932	932	Clinker {Europe without Switzerland} clinker production Cut-off, U
			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
1.8.	Silicate rock quarry waste as feeding material for enrichment in rare earth elements	α avoided emissions	Inert waste landfill (mineral waste)	0,00626	6,26	Treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill RoW
			Transport to landfill	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}
		β avoided emissions	Use of mineral resources or concentrates obtained from the processing of rare earth elements (RAEE)	20,9	20900	Rare earth carbonate concentrate {RoW} rare earth element mine operation and beneficiation, ion adsorption clays Cut-off, U
			Transport from supplier	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}

	(REE)	Symbiosis emissions	Transformation process: Rare earth element extraction (separation treatment up to mineral concentrate)	no data	no data	
			Transport from α to β	/	0,104	Transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 6 {RoW}

3.6 Analysis of symbiotic matrices

After laying out the theoretical and methodological framework, this chapter focuses on illustrating the individual IS flows identified. The matrices under study represent potential IS cases between companies operating in the following sectors: mining, ceramics, waste treatment and by-product recovery. These are mainly mineral-based flows, which can serve as both inputs and outputs in the production processes involved in the symbiotic matrices. This general overview forms the basis for the in-depth economic assessments in Chapter 5, which will present the results of the Monte Carlo simulation, sensitivity analyses, evolutionary scenarios and environmental benefits associated with symbiotic relationships.

3.6.1 Fine mineral waste for the technosoil

The fine mining waste considered in this matrix can originate from two distinct production processes:

- (1) the mechanical treatment of construction and demolition waste (CDW) and
- (2) the extraction and processing of quarry materials.

In the first case, the waste consists of the fine fraction (<4 mm) resulting from the crushing, screening and sorting of building materials, with a significant component below 0.063 mm (filler) (Manning & Vetterlein, 2004). This fraction, often accumulated in large quantities in recycling plants, has physical-chemical and mineralogical characteristics that affect its potential for use (Rodrigues et al., 2013). Recent studies have shown that CDW fines, if properly treated by removing contaminants and adding compost, can be valorised as constituents of technosoils capable of supporting plant growth and improving soil health indicators (Yilmaz et al., 2017).

In the second case, the fines come from quarrying and processing of quarry materials. These are fine-grained powders and waste generated, in this case too, by crushing and screening operations; in specifically, “quarry fines” can be defined as the fraction smaller than 0.063 mm, often consisting of fine sand, silt and clay (Clive Mitchell, 2009). Their production is inevitable and can reach up to 20-30% of the material processed, depending on the lithological type and the crushing technologies used (Clive Mitchell, 2009). Despite the difficulties in placing them on the market, quarry fines have physical and mineralogical properties that make them suitable for alternative uses, such as the formulation of artificial substrates for environmental restoration.

Both types of waste can be used to produce technosoil, i.e. artificial substrates designed to mimic the functions of natural soil and suitable for plant growth (Yilmaz et al., 2017). These substrates are used in environmental and landscape restoration projects, in the remediation of contaminated sites and in the controlled covering of landfills. The use of fine waste in technosoil makes it possible to replace virgin materials (e.g. natural soils and aggregates) and at the same time reduce waste disposal, with environmental (lower resource consumption and reduced landfill impact) and economic (lower procurement and disposal costs) benefits (Yilmaz et al., 2017).

3.6.2 Bottom ash for the cement and ceramics industries

The Municipal Incinerator Bottom Ashes (MIBA) are the main solid residue resulting from the waste-to-energy processes of non-hazardous municipal and special waste, accounting for approximately 80-90% of total residues by weight (Schabbach et al., 2012). Their typical composition includes silicon, aluminium, calcium and iron oxides, as well as traces of heavy metals; this gives the material potential interest as a secondary source of aluminosilicates for industrial applications (Schabbach et al., 2012). In recent years, thanks to recent technological advances, in particular in the field of high-temperature inertisation, it has been possible to effectively stabilise the ash, reducing the mobility of contaminating elements and making them suitable for new industrial uses. Inertised MIBA can be valorised in:

- (1) ceramic products (tiles, bricks) by mixing with clay, thus obtaining materials with

mechanical properties and water absorption comparable to those of commercial products;

- (2) alternative cementitious materials, such as alkali-activated geopolymers, thanks to the high content of glass phases rich in silica and alumina, which promote the formation of high-performance polymer matrices (Schabbach et al., 2012).

Industrial experience in Europe has already demonstrated the feasibility of using MIBA treated on a semi-industrial scale for the production of ceramic tiles and building materials (Schabbach et al., 2012), with dual environmental benefits (reduction in landfill disposal and consumption of natural raw materials) and economic benefits (reduction in procurement and disposal costs).

3.6.3 Fly ash for the creation of geopolymers for ceramic products

Municipal Solid Waste Incineration Fly Ash (MSWI FA) accounts for approximately 10% of the total residues from waste-to-energy processes (Lan et al., 2022). Unlike heavy ash, it is generally classified as hazardous waste due to its high concentration of heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Cd, Ni) and the presence of soluble salts, chlorides, sulphates and persistent organic micropollutants (dioxins and furans) (Kanhari et al., 2020; Lan et al., 2022). This necessitates preliminary treatment (washing, stabilisation, thermal or chemical inertisation) to reduce leachability and ensure environmental safety (Kanhari et al., 2020). In recent years, the possibility has emerged of exploiting MSWI FA as precursors for the synthesis of geopolymers, alternative low-carbon cementitious materials based on the polymerisation of aluminosilicate phases in a strongly alkaline environment (Lan et al., 2022). This strategy not only reduces landfill disposal but also effectively immobilises contaminants by trapping heavy metals in the glassy matrix of the geopolymer (Lan et al., 2022). SWI FA-based geopolymers have shown high durability in both acidic and alkaline conditions and excellent capacity to immobilise inorganic and organic contaminants (Lan et al., 2022). They are therefore considered a circular solution for the production of alternative cementitious materials, as well as in the field of ceramic or glass-ceramic products (Silva et al., 2017).

3.6.4 Fly ash for metal recovery

Fly ash from municipal solid waste incineration (MSWI FA), as previously mentioned, contains significant concentrations of heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Cu, Cd, Cr, Ni), generated by volatilisation and subsequent condensation during combustion (Kanhari et al., 2020). These residues, often classified as hazardous waste, represent both an environmental problem (potential metal leaching and soil and water contamination) and an important opportunity for the recovery of secondary resources (Bakalár et al., 2021). Several technological approaches have been developed for the recovery of metals from FA:

- (1) acid or aqueous leaching, with high yields (up to 80-95% for Zn, Cd, Pb and Cu) depending on the composition of the ash (Bakalár et al., 2021);
- (2) bioleaching, which uses microorganisms to extract metals, reducing the use of chemical reagents (Kanhari et al., 2020);
- (3) electrodialysis processes, which allow the selective separation of metal ions (Kanhari et al., 2020);
- (4) thermal treatments, such as vitrification, which concentrate metals in the fly ash fraction and facilitate their subsequent recovery (Izumikawa, 1996);
- (5) integrated hydrometallurgical processes, which combine leaching, extraction and adsorption, allowing yields close to 100% for some elements (Bakalár et al., 2021).

Among the main solutions applied at industrial level, in Switzerland the FLUWA and FLUREC processes enable the recovery of high-purity zinc (> 99.9%) and other precious metals with yields of between 60 and 95% (Bakalár et al., 2021). The growing interest in these technologies is linked not only to environmental aspects (reduction of toxicity, prevention of contamination and reduction of landfill use), but also to economic and social aspects. Recent studies propose a vision of metal recovery from FA as a tool for the circular economy: 1-10 kg of pure metals can be extracted from one ton of FA, simultaneously reducing the environmental impact of primary mining and generating secondary raw materials for the metallurgical, chemical and construction materials industries (Bakalár et al., 2021). The SWOT

analysis conducted by Bakalár et al. (2021) highlights that the main strengths (metal recovery, reduced toxicity, reduced environmental risk, reuse of process materials) outweigh the critical issues related to social acceptability, regulatory complexity and treatment costs.

3.6.5 Fired ceramic waste for the ceramic and cement industries

Fired ceramic waste generated by the ceramic industry (tiles, stoneware, bricks, porcelain) accounts for a significant proportion of production residues: it is estimated that around 15-30% of the materials used become waste in the form of defective, broken or non-compliant pieces that can no longer be reintroduced into the production cycle (Chang et al., 2023a). In the main European production districts, this percentage translates into tens of thousands of tonnes per year, traditionally sent to landfill or used in low value-added applications. From a compositional point of view, fired ceramic waste is characterised by an aluminosilicate matrix, rich in SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 , with variable contents of CaO , Fe_2O_3 and alkalis, and mineral phases such as quartz and mullite (Fu & Lee, 2024; Fugazzotto et al., 2023). These properties allow it to be exploited in various fields:

- (1) production of new ceramic products, partially replacing clays and feldspars in the manufacture of tiles and bricks (Planelles-Aragó et al., s.d.);
- (2) Cementitious materials and concrete, as ceramic powders can be used as aggregates or pozzolanic additives, also ensuring good mechanical strength (Chang et al., 2023b).

Pilot projects, such as the Spanish RECERCO project, have confirmed the feasibility of reintroducing fired ceramic waste both in the ceramic sector (new tiles) and in related fields (composites for construction), with an estimated potential of over 78,000 tonnes per year of waste that can be redirected to new production cycles (Planelles-Aragó et al., s.d.).

3.6.6 Industrial mineral waste for technical soil and/or base material for footing tracks

The granite and marble mining industry generates huge quantities of solid waste during cutting, polishing and crushing operations. It is estimated that almost half of the extracted material is waste in the form of fragments, dust and sludge (Hamza et al., 2011). These residues, which are mainly carbonaceous and siliceous-feldspathic in nature, pose significant environmental problems if disposed of in landfills or abandoned in areas adjacent to quarries, due to their high alkalinity and tendency to disperse dust into the atmosphere (Hamza et al., 2011). In recent years, several studies have demonstrated the possibility of exploiting this waste as mineral components for the formulation of technosoils, artificial substrates designed for environmental recovery and the redevelopment of degraded areas (Yilmaz et al., 2017). Their inert nature and variable grain size make these residues particularly suitable for use as a mineral skeleton in technosoils, helping to ensure structural stability, drainage capacity and porosity. When mixed with organic fractions such as compost, treated sludge or biochar, they can recreate substrates suitable for plant growth in compromised areas, such as disused quarries, landfills or urban brownfields (Tazzini et al., 2024; Yilmaz et al., 2017). In addition to these applications, which are the focus of the NODES project, marble and granite waste can also be used as:

- (1) aggregates in concrete and road sub-bases (Ahmed et al., 2020);
- (2) mineral additives for concrete and mortar, improving durability and resistance to sulphates and chlorides (Ulubeyli et al., 2016);
- (3) raw materials for bricks and cement blocks, with up to 40% replacement, while maintaining mechanical performance compatible with industrial standards (Hamza et al., 2011);
- (4) industrial fillers for paper, plastics, rubber and pharmaceuticals, thanks to the high carbon purity of marble sludge (Tazzini et al., 2024).

The use of quarry waste in techno-soils and building materials reduces landfill disposal, enhances secondary resources and contributes to replacing non-renewable natural aggregates. This is perfectly in line with the principles of the circular economy and European policies for reducing extractive waste, while promoting the sustainability of the stone industry and the regeneration of extractive areas.

3.6.7 Coarse mineral waste for certifiable aggregates

Coarse mineral waste from CDW and quarrying or excavation activities represents a significant fraction of the residues produced by the construction and mining sectors. By definition, this category includes materials larger than 4 mm, such as gravel and coarse aggregates (Zhang et al., 2020). In the case of CDW, a substantial part of this waste consists of crushed concrete, bricks, mortar and stone fragments, the percentage of which depends on the type of demolition (Ossa et al., 2016). Normally, these materials are sent to landfill, with significant environmental and economic costs. However, with appropriate treatment (removal of impurities, crushing and screening), they can be used to produce certifiable recycled aggregates that are suitable for replacing natural aggregates in numerous applications:

- (1) road sub-base layers (Zhang et al., 2020);
- (2) cement conglomerates and concrete: studies have shown that it is possible to replace up to 20-40% of natural aggregates with recycled ones, without compromising mechanical properties (Ossa et al., 2016);
- (3) bituminous mixtures for urban paving: up to 20% of aggregates from CDW can be used in asphalt conglomerates for base and wearing courses (Ossa et al., 2016).
- (1) Likewise, coarse waste from quarrying activities can be treated and reused as alternative aggregates: recent studies have highlighted benefits not only in terms of replacing natural resources, but also the possibility of carbon capture and storage, up to 16 g of CO₂ per brick (Khamis et al., 2024).

3.6.8 Silicate rock quarry waste for rare earth enrichment

Silicate rocks (granite, basalt and other intrusive or volcanic rocks) exploited in mining activities generate large quantities of solid waste. This waste poses a significant environmental problem due to the large quantities involved, but it can also be a secondary resource as it contains rare earth elements (REE) and other strategic metals (Pyrgaki et al., 2021). In Europe, where there is still no established industrial production of rare earths, the recovery of extractive waste from silicate rocks is considered a promising way to reduce supply risks, particularly in the renewable energy, electric mobility and high-tech sectors (Pyrgaki et al., 2021). REE concentrations in silicate waste vary widely depending on the geological and mineralogical context, with values reported in the literature ranging from a few tens to thousands of ppm (Pyrgaki et al., 2021). In fact, depending on the treatment processes, REE recovery rates from extractive waste typically range between 20 and 50%, thanks to acid leaching, bioleaching and hydrometallurgical separation techniques. Although not yet consolidated on an industrial scale, these values highlight the potential for exploiting silicate waste as a secondary resource.

3.7 Economic and environmental results analysis

This chapter is at the heart of the cost-benefit analysis applied to the NODOES project. It dives into the economic and environmental outcomes that come from simulating potential IS relationships identified in the area, aiming to measure their cost-effectiveness and overall impact from a broader perspective. The analysis contrasts the BAU scenario with an alternative scenario where IS is put into action. For each production matrix identified, the avoided costs (disposal, procurement), the additional costs associated with cooperation (transport, treatment, coordination), and the environmental benefits that can be monetised through shadow pricing of avoided emissions are evaluated.

The assessment leans on a quantitative approach that combines real data, technical-economic estimates, and Monte Carlo simulations to paint a clear and realistic picture of the sustainability of these symbiotic relationships. The findings are expressed in terms of Net Present Value (NPV), showcasing the conditions under which can yield benefits for both the companies involved and the surrounding community. The chapter therefore represents a fundamental step in guiding the strategic choices of businesses and policymakers, offering a quantitative basis for evaluating interventions inspired by the CE and the valorisation of industrial waste.

3.7.1 Economic analysis

This section takes a closer look at the financial viability of IS relationships within the NODES territory. Using the methodological framework outlined in the earlier chapters, the NPV is calculated as a summary indicator of the project's profitability compared to the BAU scenario. The economic outcomes were derived from Monte Carlo simulations, which utilises technical and economic data gathered for each matrix analysed. The approach adopted takes into account the critical variables that influence the costs and benefits of implementing IS, also integrating alternative scenarios to test the robustness of the initial assumptions.

The economic analysis is divided into four subsections:

- (1) Base NPV and cost allocation. This first sub-section presents the static NPV derived from the simulation for each symbiotic pair. The NPV reflects the balance between the expected economic benefits (costs avoided for disposal and procurement of raw materials) and the extra costs needed to achieve the synergy (transport, treatment, coordination). A key part of the analysis is the allocation of additional costs between the two companies involved, modelled using the parameter λ . To explore this, different cost-sharing configurations were simulated in order to see how the NPV varies depending on whether the costs are borne fully by the waste producer, by the waste user, or shared equally.
- (2) Sensitivity analysis. To ensure the economic results hold up against uncertainties in the input parameters, a sensitivity analysis was conducted focusing on the main factors that influence the NPV: waste treatment costs, virgin material purchase costs, technical production and consumption rates ($W \alpha$ and $R \beta$), investment time horizon, and discount rate used for discounting.
- (3) Impact of company size. Another aspect investigated concerns the role of company size in determining the economic value of symbiosis. By classifying companies as micro, small, medium and large (according to EU Directive 2023/2775), it was possible to simulate different producer-user combinations to assess whether and how the scale of operations influences the final result.
- (4) Inflation and technological innovation. These two exogenous factors shape outcomes over the medium to long term. The inclusion of these scenarios allows to understand the dynamics of the symbiotic system and to evaluate how resilient these collaborations are as time goes on.

This economic analysis therefore provides a quantitative view of the conditions of balance between the costs and benefits of IS, setting the stage for a deeper look at environmental impacts (Section 5.2).

3.7.1.1 Base NPV and cost allocation

The static NPV analysis of the various IS relationships shows a generally positive trend, confirming the economic feasibility of the symbiotic collaborations planned in the NODES territory. In most of the cases examined (RM 1.1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.5, 1.6), the NPV is positive, indicating a favourable situation for the companies involved: symbiosis shows its value in avoiding disposal and procurement costs so high that they offset the additional costs generated by the interaction. In these situations, the division of symbiotic costs (such as transport, treatment and coordination) can be done fairly, without compromising the convenience of either party. However, it is important to note some significant exceptions. For example, in the case of RM 1.3, despite having a positive NPV, the margin is quite slim, making the project more susceptible to changes in economic and technical parameters. In such cases, the distribution of costs becomes crucial, as even small imbalances can make the collaboration unsustainable for one of the two parties, particularly for the manufacturing company (α). Another case that emerged is that of RM 1.7, where the NPV of the project is positive, but for the user company β the collaboration is not so economically advantageous, since the costs of processing secondary materials are higher than the savings from not buying virgin raw materials. This scenario underscores the need for specific incentive models or asymmetric cost agreements, to make these partnerships work. Even in the case of RM 1.6, although the overall NPV is positive, it can be seen that economic equilibrium is only achieved if the manufacturing company bears most of the extra costs. This shows that, even in situations with potential synergies, the perception of fairness in the sharing of benefits and costs can

be crucial to the success of the initiative. Furthermore, it is important to note that in some cases (RM 1.1 and 1.4), the lack of specific data for certain ATECO codes led to the use of proxies from available sectors, which could introduce margins of uncertainty in the results. On the other hand, for RM 1.8, sufficient data for this symbiosis could not be found, so it was not possible to perform a complete analysis as in the other cases.

In summary, the analysis shows that the economic profitability of symbiotic relationships is generally robust but can be quite sensitive to the cost structure and how those costs are allocated among the parties involved. Specifically, projects with high avoided costs for α tend to yield a positive NPV even in the presence of significant symbiosis costs. On the other hand, projects with low margins or high impacts on treatment costs for β require more sophisticated contractual balancing solutions to ensure fair and sustainable participation. These results highlight the importance of a thorough analysis of the economic and technological context of the companies involved, as well as the need for collaborative and flexible design of symbiotic agreements.

3.7.1.2 Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis was performed to test how robust the NPV is to changes in the most significant technical and economic parameters. The aim is to understand how the results of the economic analysis may change as operating conditions vary, identifying the most relevant risk factors for the sustainability of symbiotic relationships.

The simulations clearly show that the most sensitive parameter is the cost of processing the waste: even a modest increase (e.g. +10%) can jeopardise the economic viability for the user company, as seen in cases RM 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.7. This shows that, without logistical and processing efficiencies, symbiosis can lose its appeal for those receiving the material, especially if the benefits of replacing virgin raw materials are not significant. On the other hand, changes in technical rates ($W \alpha$ and $R \beta$) did not have a significant impact on most of the symbioses examined. This suggests that economic results remain relatively stable with respect to fluctuations in standard production performance, at least within the ranges considered.

With regard to financial parameters, changes in both the discount rate and the project time horizon had a marginal impact on NPV results in most cases. The structure of costs and benefits over time appears sufficiently balanced to make the results resilient to these variations. However, in the case of projects with a low economic margin (e.g. RM 1.3) or significant asymmetries in the distribution of benefits, even moderate variations in the input parameters can significantly alter the sustainability of the symbiosis, making it necessary to exercise greater caution in defining agreements between the parties. In some cases (e.g. RM 1.7), it is noted that sensitivity to the cost of virgin raw materials can influence the perceived convenience for the user: an increase in the market price of alternative materials could significantly improve the attractiveness of the symbiosis.

In summary, the sensitivity analysis highlighted that transformation costs are the main economic risk factor, so it is important to consider risk mitigation tools such as compensation funds, public incentives and flexible agreements to ensure the viability of projects that are most vulnerable to changes in the NODES context.

3.7.1.3 Impact of company size

The analysis of the impact of the size of the companies involved aims to explore whether and how the operational scale of the participating companies affects the profitability of symbiotic relationships. In particular, different combinations of micro, small, medium and large companies were simulated, following the EU classification, to observe the resulting NPV variations. In general, symbiosis is economically sustainable for all size categories, especially in cases where the benefits from avoided costs (such as disposal for α or procurement for β) are significant (e.g., RM 1.1, 1.4, 1.5). In these situations, even small businesses can benefit from collaboration, thanks to a cost structure that works in their favour.

However, there are some critical issues related to company size that emerge in specific cases. In RM 1.2, the interaction between a medium-sized company α and a micro-sized company β can lead to a negative NPV for the user. This happens when the costs of symbiosis are not distributed fairly in relation to the operational capacities of the companies, making the

investment too burdensome for the smaller company. A similar effect can be observed in RM 1.3, where micro or small enterprises struggle to bear the costs necessary to activate the symbiosis, even if the overall NPV is positive. In these cases, public intervention or the adoption of compensation mechanisms is essential to facilitate access to symbiosis for smaller enterprises. Conversely, in the case of RM 1.7, it is clear that even small manufacturing companies can achieve positive economic results if they collaborate with larger users, thanks to the potential savings on high disposal costs. These observations suggest that the size of companies is not in itself an obstacle to symbiosis but can significantly influence how benefits and costs are distributed. Therefore, to ensure fair participation, it is important to carefully assess the proportionality of cost sharing in relation to the operational and financial capacities of companies. In addition, it would be appropriate to introduce specific support tools for small businesses, such as incentives or technical assistance services. In conclusion, company size is a critical factor to consider in the operational design of symbiosis, especially to ensure fairness and the real feasibility of the proposed solutions.

3.7.1.4 Inflation and technological innovation

In addition to the technical and economic parameters internal to the project, the analysis took into account two external factors of a macroeconomic and technological nature that may influence the economic balance of symbiotic relationships in the medium to long term: inflation and technological innovation. Inflation was seen as a gradual increase in operating costs over time, particularly with regard to transport, waste treatment and raw material procurement. In most of the cases examined, inflation tends to favour the adoption of IS, as rising costs make alternatives (such as disposal or the purchase of virgin inputs) less advantageous in the long term. From this perspective, symbiosis becomes an effective strategy for containing costs and increasing the resilience of businesses, especially when supported by stable contracts.

On the other hand, technological innovation has more complex effects. On the one hand, it can improve the efficiency of production processes, reducing waste rates ($W \alpha$) for the manufacturing company or input consumption ($R \beta$) for the user. However, this improvement can also reduce the amount of residue available for symbiosis, undermining the material basis of symbiotic exchange. This effect is particularly evident in case RM 1.1, where the decrease in waste production by α , following a technological improvement, leads to a significant drop in NPV, due to the lower input substitution by β . In some cases (such as RM 1.2, 1.3, 1.5), the impact of technological innovation appears to be less pronounced, but it is still an aspect to keep an eye on over time, especially from a forward-looking perspective.

It is important to note that, of the two effects, technological innovation tends to have a more structural and lasting impact than inflation, which can be more unpredictable and situational. The interaction between these two factors suggests that there is a real opportunity to adopt dynamic strategies to manage their symbiosis, which could include: regular review of economic agreements between the parties involved; the inclusion of clauses for cost adjustment or sharing of efficiency benefits; the integration of technological planning tools and evolving scenarios into the ex ante assessment of initiatives.

In summary, while inflation tends to increase the attractiveness of symbiosis over time, technological innovation, while beneficial in absolute terms, can weaken the material basis for collaboration. This requires greater managerial and contractual flexibility to ensure economic sustainability.

3.7.2 Environmental analysis

The adoption of IS practices not only brings economic benefits to the companies involved, but also has a very positive environmental impact, particularly thanks to the reduction in greenhouse gas emissions. In this section, we will present the results of the environmental analysis carried out on the symbiotic relationships identified, focusing on the quantification of avoided emissions and their monetisation through the use of carbon pricing. Before proceeding, it should be noted that, due to a lack of available data, it was not possible to reach definitive conclusions for RM 1.4 and RM 1.8, so the results presented below will be the conclusions reached for the remaining RMs.

The results of the Monte Carlo simulation offer a more discordant view than the economic

analysis. In particular, for almost all the material relationships examined, the net present environmental value is negative, indicating that the additional emissions generated by the transformation processes outweigh the environmental benefits of symbiotic practices. Only RM 1.5 shows a positive environmental NPV, but it is limited in scope and strongly influenced by the equitable distribution of environmental costs between the two companies involved. In fact, if the environmental benefits are not distributed evenly, the advantage for one of the parties could disappear. In general, the results highlight that, for this type of waste (mineral or inorganic), reuse processes generate significant emissions, which are not fully offset by the savings derived from replacing virgin raw materials. This is because, unlike other supply chains that contain large amounts of organic or energy-rich material, the materials in question do not produce high emissions when stored in quarries and, above all, require treatments that consume a lot of energy or have a high environmental impact. The environmental analysis gave a negative result, which invites us to reflect on the method used for the impact analysis. The damage to the environment caused by these flows is not limited to greenhouse gas emissions, but also includes other significant impact categories, in particular erosion and soil consumption. In short, environmental analysis based solely on carbon footprint shows that symbiotic relationships for the RM 1 family do not offer significant advantages in terms of emissions, except on rare occasions. This does not imply that they have no environmental value, but rather that carbon is not the most significant impact for these flows. It is essential to consider additional environmental indicators for a more comprehensive assessment, in order to examine the potential environmental benefits of symbiosis through a multi-criteria perspective, beyond CO₂ alone.

3.8 Summary of results and future prospects

This chapter brings together the final reflections of the analysis, summarising the main results that came out of the economic and environmental assessments done as part of the NODES project. After testing the model on a set of potential material relationships, here's a critical assessment of the tool's opportunities and limits, keeping in mind the assumptions made and the areas for improvement that were found.

The analysis took an experimental approach, useful for validating a model that can be applied on a territorial scale and transferred to real contexts. With this in mind, the chapter concludes with some operational and methodological ideas for future applications of the model, both in the design phase and in the implementation of CE policies.

3.8.1 Summary of results

The CBA made it possible to systematically examine the sustainability of IS relationships in the NODES territory, highlighting their economic and environmental implications.

From an economic point of view, most of the simulated material relationships showed a positive NPV, indicating potential benefits for the companies involved. In particular, the relationships involving high disposal costs avoided for the α company and procurement costs avoided for the β company are economically advantageous, even if there are significant symbiosis costs. But, the division of costs between companies (transport, treatment, coordination) emerges as a very critical element in maintaining the balance of the relationship: if the division is unfair, the NPV can become negative for one of the two parties. The results are generally robust even in the face of variations in technical and financial parameters, but show a strong sensitivity to transformation costs, particularly for company β . The company size does not directly affect the sustainability of the project, but it can have an impact on the ability to bear the initial costs or access economies of scale. External factors such as inflation and technological innovation can significantly affect the economic balance over time, making flexible and responsive contract operations desirable.

On the other hand, the environmental analysis provided completely opposite results. Using an approach based on shadow pricing of CO₂ emissions, it emerged that, for most of the relationships examined (particularly those related to the mineral matrix), the environmental NPV is negative. This is because the transformation processes required for symbiosis produce more emissions than the BAU scenario. Only in very specific situations, such as RM 1.5, is there a net benefit in terms of emissions, but this is still a marginal advantage and strongly

influenced by the distribution of environmental costs. The analysis revealed that, for these types of waste, climate impact is not the most relevant factor. Impacts related to land use, erosion or material dispersion could be more significant, suggesting the need to integrate more comprehensive LCA-based approaches.

In summary, the analysis showed that symbiotic relationships have interesting economic potential, while the environmental benefits remain uncertain and depend on the type of waste and the method of recovery. This confirms the usefulness of the model as a preventive assessment tool but also highlights the importance of adopting a multidimensional view of sustainability.

3.8.2 Model limits

Although it has produced interesting and useful results, the CBA model developed and applied in the NODES context has some structural and operational limitations. These limitations are related to data availability and the methodological choices made. Nevertheless, these limitations do not compromise the overall validity of the model; rather, they define its scope of application and offer ideas for future improvements.

In several cases, it was necessary to rely on industry averages or proxies from companies with similar ATECO codes, as specific data from the companies themselves was not available. Technical rates were also estimated on an annual and static basis, without considering possible seasonal variations or irregular production cycles. Although this approach was consistent with an experimental phase, it introduced a degree of uncertainty into the results. Cooperation has also been simplified, not taking into consideration relational, behavioural or organisational aspects that, in reality, have a significant impact on the IS success. For example, factors such as trust between companies, willingness to share data and the ability to negotiate fair agreements are not considered. Furthermore, regulatory, logistical or administrative barriers that can hold back implementation, even when there are theoretical economic benefits, are also missing. The environmental assessment is one-dimensional, focusing only on climate impact (CO₂ equivalent) and overlooking other categories that are important for the types of waste analysed, such as soil erosion, as mentioned above. This has probably disadvantaged some relationships (e.g. RM 1.1 – RM 1.4), which produce environmental benefits not directly linked to emissions reduction but still considerable in a circular sustainability context. The analysis was conducted over a ten-year time horizon, but with essentially static parameters. Evolutionary scenarios such as regulatory changes or the systemic effects of the spread of symbiosis in the territory were not taken into account. The current structure, although useful for an ex ante assessment, does not integrate adaptive dynamics that would be desirable during planning or monitoring. These limitations offer valuable insights for improving the model, especially if we consider it as a decision-making tool in real-life situations. In the next section, perspectives for addressing these critical issues will be discussed.

3.8.3 Future perspectives

The CBA application model to potential symbiotic relationships in the NODES territory represented an important opportunity to experiment with new methodologies. The objective was to evaluate not only the sustainability of individual interactions, but also the effectiveness of the tool in supporting the design of new synergies between companies. During the analysis, a key point became clear: although based on simplified assumptions, the model proved to be applicable in real contexts.

It is suitable for assessing in advance the economic and environmental benefits of an exchange between businesses, even without detailed data, and it can be easily adapted if more specific information is available on two (or more) companies operating in the area. It is designed to be replicable on a territorial scale and potentially integrated into local governance tools for the circular economy. In this regard, the use of simulation data made it possible to test and validate the functioning of the model. However, its true potential is realised when it is applied to real data provided by companies interested in establishing a symbiotic collaboration. In these situations, the model can offer concrete support to the negotiations between the parties through an analysis of the distributed benefits/costs.

Looking to the future, the model can be further strengthened by following these points:

- (1) The integration of multi-impact LCA methods to examine other environmental categories beyond CO₂, such as soil erosion or land use;
- (2) Dynamic simulation modules that consider the evolution of regulatory changes over time;
- (3) The digitisation of the tool to make it accessible to businesses, public bodies and local facilitators through intuitive interfaces and automated calculations;
- (4) Integration into IS platforms as technical and operational support for evaluating the opportunities mapped.

In conclusion, the model developed represents a concrete step towards the creation of applicable and action-oriented assessment tools capable of guiding businesses and institutions in the transition towards more sustainable models as desired by the NODES project.

Bibliography

- Ahmed, H., Abdelhaffez, G., & Ahmed, A. (2020). Potential use of marble and granite solid wastes as environmentally friendly coarse particulate in civil constructions. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 19, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-020-03014-2>
- Azevedo-Lopes, T., Queiroz, H. M., Ruiz, F., Asensio, V., Ferreira, A. D., Cherubin, M. R., & Ferreira, T. O. (2024). From waste to soil: Technosols made with construction and demolition waste as a nature-based solution for land reclamation. *Waste Management*, 186, 153–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2024.06.010>
- Bakalár, T., Pavolová, H., Hajduová, Z., Lacko, R., & Kyšela, K. (2021). Metal recovery from municipal solid waste incineration fly ash as a tool of circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 302, 126977. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126977>
- Chang, Q., Liu, L., Farooqi, M. U., Thomas, B., & Özkılıç, Y. O. (2023a). Data-driven based estimation of waste-derived ceramic concrete from experimental results with its environmental assessment. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, 24, 6348–6368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2023.04.223>
- Chang, Q., Liu, L., Farooqi, M. U., Thomas, B., & Özkılıç, Y. O. (2023b). Data-driven based estimation of waste-derived ceramic concrete from experimental results with its environmental assessment. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, 24, 6348–6368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2023.04.223>
- Clive Mitchell. (2009). *Quarry Fines and Waste (Quarries & Mines)*. British Geological Survey.
- Fu, S., & Lee, J. (2024). Recycling of ceramic tile waste into construction materials. *Developments in the Built Environment*, 18, 100431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dibe.2024.100431>
- Fugazzotto, M., Mazzoleni, P., Lancellotti, I., Camerini, R., Ferrari, P., Tiné, M. R., Centauro, I., Salvatici, T., & Barone, G. (2023). Industrial Ceramics: From Waste to New Resources for Eco-Sustainable Building Materials. *Minerals*, 13(6), 815. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min13060815>
- Hamza, R., El-Haggar, S., & Khedr, S. (2011). Marble and Granite Waste: Characterization and Utilization in Concrete Bricks. *International Journal of Bioscience, Biochemistry and Bioinformatics*, 1, 286–291. <https://doi.org/10.7763/IJBBB.2011.V1.54>
- Izumikawa, C. (1996). Metal recovery from fly ash generated from vitrification process for MSW ash. *Waste Management*, 16(5), 501–507. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0956-053X\(96\)00092-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0956-053X(96)00092-X)
- Kanhar, A. H., Chen, S., & Wang, F. (2020). Incineration Fly Ash and Its Treatment to Possible Utilization: A Review. *Energies*, 13(24), 6681. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13246681>
- Khamis, M. A. A., Kusin, F. M., & Iskandar, I. (2024). Mining waste as an alternative aggregate in brick production for carbon capture and storage. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1369(1), 012014. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1369/1/012014>
- Lan, T., Meng, Y., Ju, T., Chen, Z., Du, Y., Deng, Y., Song, M., Han, S., & Jiang, J. (2022). Synthesis and application of geopolymers from municipal waste incineration fly ash (MSWI FA) as raw ingredient—A review. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 182, 106308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106308>
- Manning, D. A. C., & Vetterlein, J. (2004). *Exploitation and Use of Quarry Fines*.
- Ossa, A., García, J. L., & Botero, E. (2016). Use of recycled construction and demolition waste (CDW) aggregates: A sustainable alternative for the pavement construction industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135, 379–386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.088>
- Planelles-Aragó, J., Lázaro, V., Noguera, J. F., Pérez-Argilés, M., López-Rius, B., Pérez-Quiles, V., & Poveda, J. (s.d.). VALORISATION OF FIRED CERAMIC TILE WASTE IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR.
- Produzione in valore e quantità per tutti i prodotti (Prodcom). (s.d.). Recuperato 4 agosto 2025, da https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/it/dw/categories/IT1,Z0600IND,1.0/IND_PRODUCTION/DCSP_PRODCOM/IT1,115_168_DF_DCSP_PRODCOM_3,1.0
- Pyrgaki, K., Gemeni, V., Karkalis, C., Koukouzas, N., Koutsovitis, P., & Petrounias, P. (2021). Geochemical Occurrence of Rare Earth Elements in Mining Waste and Mine Water: A Review. *Minerals*, 11(8), 860. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min11080860>
- Rodrigues, F., Carvalho, M. T., Evangelista, L., & de Brito, J. (2013). Physical–chemical and mineralogical characterization of fine aggregates from construction and demolition waste

recycling plants. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 52, 438–445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.02.023>

Schabbach, L. M., Andreola, F., Barbieri, L., Lancellotti, I., Karamanova, E., Ranguelov, B., & Karamanov, A. (2012). Post-treated incinerator bottom ash as alternative raw material for ceramic manufacturing. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 32(11), 2843–2852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2012.01.020>

Silva, R. V., de Brito, J., Lynn, C. J., & Dhir, R. K. (2017). Use of municipal solid waste incineration bottom ashes in alkali-activated materials, ceramics and granular applications: A review. *Waste Management*, 68, 207–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.06.043>

Tazzini, A., Gambino, F., Casale, M., & Dino, G. A. (2024). Managing Marble Quarry Waste: Opportunities and Challenges for Circular Economy Implementation. *Sustainability*, 16(7), 3056. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16073056>

Ulubeyli, G. C., Bilir, T., & Artir, R. (2016). Durability Properties of Concrete Produced by Marble Waste as Aggregate or Mineral Additives. *Procedia Engineering*, 161, 543–548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2016.08.689>

Yazan, D. M., & Fraccascia, L. (2020). Sustainable operations of industrial symbiosis: An enterprise input-output model integrated by agent-based simulation. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(2), 392–414. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2019.1590660>

Yilmaz, D., Peyneau, P.-E., Beaudet, L., Cannavo, P., & Sere, G. (2017). Assessment of hydraulics properties of technosoil constructed with waste material using Beerkan infiltration. 13958. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2017EGUGA..1913958Y>

Zhang, J., Ding, L., Li, F., & Peng, J. (2020). Recycled aggregates from construction and demolition wastes as alternative filling materials for highway subgrades in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 255, 120223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120223>

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

NODES
Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile